

REBOOT
EUROPEAN FILM COMPETITIVENESS

D7.12 REPORT ON MILESTONE TOOLS

Project: Reviving, Boosting, Optimising and Transforming European Film Competitiveness - REBOOT

Grant Agreement: 101094796 - HORIZON-CL2-2022-HERITAGE-01

Author(s): Gentiana Ramadani (UNIVIE), Daniel Biltereyst (UGent), Laia Comerma (ELIAMEP), Mafalda Dâmaso (EUR), Tuuli Lähdesmäki (JYU), Arianna Martinelli (SSSA), Alexia Mitsikostas (ELIAMEP), Piergiorgio Pilo (SSSA), Fernando Ramos (UCM), Marcin Sobieszczanski (UCA), Jean-François Trubert (UCA), Pelin Turan (SSSA), Antonios Vlassis (ULIEGE)

Reviewer(s): Katharine Sarikakis (UNIVIE), Angeliki Chatziefrimidou (UNIVIE)

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1. PROJECT DESCRIPTION

This report is part of the REBOOT project (Reviving, Boosting, Optimising and Transforming European Film Competitiveness), which focuses on the European audiovisual sector and its film industry. The REBOOT project aims to connect their strengths, identify and overcome weaknesses, and plan for future competitiveness in the fields of policy, practices and experiences. More concretely, the project's objectives are, on the one hand, to explore the long-standing strengths and pervasive gaps in European audiovisual competitiveness and policies for competitiveness-including ways of 'measuring', 'analysing' and 'evaluating' the impact of policies and strategic pathways. The project aspires to focus attention on actively preparing for the future by exploring audience preferences and how these are generated, as well as modes of film content production.

The latter are elements which today's youth will carry and engage with in the coming decades as makers and consumers, as well as industry and policy leaders. The project therefore interrogates the 'what is', but also the 'what has been' and 'what will be' through fresh lenses. REBOOT aims to provide a holistic overview of the European film industry, focusing on maximising its existing strengths while developing strategies and tactics to optimise the potential of European youth audiences, both as emerging viewers and as engaged citizens. Specifically, the project's goals combine several dimensions which reinforce each other but are listed separately (and in no particular order) for analytical purposes: a) increasing support intended to increase young people's engagement with European film; b) strengthening the position of the European Union (EU) in the global audiovisual economy, particularly in light of the rise of video-on-demand; c) supporting cultural diversity in the EU film industry; d) addressing the need for a different understanding of competitiveness and relevant indicators in this context; and e) recognising and supporting the importance for the EU of film and, more broadly, of the cultural and creative sector as a geopolitical asset.

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2. EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

Deliverable 7.12 – *Report on Milestone Tools* belongs to the Work Package 7 (Dissemination) and provides a detailed account of the project's progress up to the completion of Milestone 5-M24. The project's milestone plan consists of a total of seven milestones, guiding the implementation and evaluation of key activities throughout its duration.

This report covers the achievements of the first five milestones during the period M1-M24, outlining the significant steps taken to ensure the project's advancement. The report starts with Milestone 1, marking the official kick-off event. As part of Milestone 2, the project team successfully developed and launched the project website, serving as a central platform for communication and dissemination. The next step, Milestone 3, involved organising a methodology workshop, fostering alignment on research approaches and strategies among project members.

Building on these foundational activities, Milestone 4 represented the first wave of outcomes, culminating in the 1st Interim Conference in February 2024. This event provided an opportunity for partners to present early findings, exchange insights, and refine project directions. Progress continued with Milestone 5, which marked the second wave of outcomes through the organization of the 2nd Interim Conference in January 2025. During this event, members of the Project Coordination Committee convened to assess the project's trajectory, discuss preliminary results, and evaluate the next steps leading to the project's completion.

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3. MILESTONE 1 – KICK-OFF UNIVIE (M1): KICK-OFF MEETING & ALL WPs LAUNCHED

The REBOOT project officially launched with a successful kick-off meeting held from March 6th to 8th 2023 in Vienna, hosted by the University of Vienna. The event brought together all consortium partners, with 23 participants attending in person, 14 joining online, and 10 advisory board members contributing with their expertise. Over the course of three days, discussions focused on the project's strategic directions and key objectives.

The meeting commenced with an opening speech by the project coordinator, Prof. Katharine Sarikakis from the University of Vienna. Prof. Sarikakis emphasised that the issues tackled by the project represent some of the most critical societal challenges of the 21st century. She highlighted the project's potential to promote European cultural activity and cultural diversity by advancing knowledge on the needs and development of the European filmmaking industry.

After the opening remarks by the REBOOT coordinator, Prof. Sarikakis, Carla Rocha Gomes, Project Officer at the European Research Executive Agency (REA.C1) -Inclusive Society, provided an overview of the agency's mission, mandate, and expected outcomes. She outlined the procedural framework that partners and the consortium must follow, ensuring compliance with Horizon Europe's regulations.

Ms. Gomes explained key aspects of project management, including reporting guidelines, amendment procedures, and strategies for effective communication, dissemination, and exploitation of research results. Additionally, she emphasised the importance of open access to publications coming from REBOOT, proper research data management, and adherence to ethical standards.

Her presentation served as a valuable resource for consortium members, clarifying essential processes and reinforcing best practices for the successful execution of the project.

A highlight of the meeting was the participation of advisory board members. Iris Zappe-Heller, Deputy Director of the Austrian Film Institute, shared valuable insights on policies aimed at addressing gender inequalities in the film industry.

At the conclusion of the kick-off meeting, following the presentation of tasks and deliverables by all partners, the consortium established key procedures to ensure effective project coordination and

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compliance with European Commission requirements. The administrative framework was finalised, with each partner making necessary adjustments to their work packages before submitting amendments for approval. To streamline project management, a shared Google Drive was set up for documentation access, and a structured table of tasks and deliverables was cross-checked in line with the Grant Agreement.

In terms of dissemination, all partners committed to contributing at least one blog post per year, while creative collaborations were encouraged, allowing students and researchers to engage through written pieces, videos, and other materials. The next in-person consortium meeting was scheduled for May 13-16, 2024, in Nice/Cannes, with logistical arrangements managed by Cote D'Azur University. Additionally, monthly online meetings will take place during the first six months, transitioning to a quarterly format from October 2023 onwards.

Ethical considerations remain a priority, with the creation of a joint database for stakeholders and interviewees, ensuring compliance with GDPR and European consent form regulations. These measures will support the consortium's overall goal of fostering collaboration, transparency, and effective project implementation.

Photos from the Kick-Off Meeting (March 2023)

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5. MILESTONE 2 – WEBSITE UNIVIE (M3): LAUNCH OF WEBSITE; REGULAR UPDATES

As part of Task 7.1, the coordinator in cooperation with the consortium has successfully developed and launched the project website, which serves as a central platform for disseminating information about the consortium’s activities. In alignment with the task objectives, the website is regularly updated with news from partners, research findings, data, reports, and quarterly newsletter ensuring continuous engagement with stakeholders. It functions as a key tool for public outreach, enhancing visibility and accessibility to project outputs as they become available.

Screenshots from the project’s website, <https://thereboot-project.eu/>

6. MILESTONE 3 – METHODOLOGY WORKSHOP SSSA (M3): RESEARCH DESIGN CONSOLIDATION

Milestone 3 was an integral part of the research activities of the SSSA team. This milestone was designed as a “research design/methodology workshop” that brought together the REBOOT researchers, the Advisory Board members of the REBOOT project and representatives of various

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stakeholders. It was dedicated to refining the research methodology adopted for the investigation of the current international, regional, EU and national legal frameworks informing and governing the European Film Industry (EFI). Therefore, the milestone and the aforementioned workshop provided a space for interdisciplinary discussions on the efficacy of the methodology adopted by the REBOOT researchers to successfully achieve these goals.

In this regard, this milestone was closely associated, mainly, with Task 3.1 - EU and comparative mapping of the filmmaking regulatory framework. It, indeed, is related to the first stage of Task 3.1 (Months 1-12), which is allocated to data collection via desk-based research, mainly by adopting a systematic and thematic literature review, on the one hand, and systematic mapping of public regulatory sources, on the other. As a complementary to the desk-based research described as such, Milestone 3 was designed and held as a workshop aimed at bringing together the Advisory Board of the Project, project partners and key representatives of the European Film Industry (EFI) to have an open discussion and to receive feedback from the industry's perspective on the main problems faced by the EFI. It was aimed at helping to triangulate the data initially collected by holding deliberative exercises with the representatives of the key stakeholders of the EFI. To achieve this goal, SSSA has shared the preliminary results of the desk-based research with the REBOOT partner institutions and advisory board members in the second month of the project (March 2023) as a prerequisite to the workshop. During the workshop, SSSA presented the methodological choices to fulfil the research undertaken by Task 3.1 and to share the aforementioned preliminary results of the research to receive feedback based on the expertise and experiences of the audience.

This workshop served as a unique opportunity for SSSA to hear and gain insight into the perspectives and sector-specific challenges faced by the EFI given the contributions from the representatives of the EFI. By the end of the Roundtable Discussions, SSSA received constructive criticism of and suggestions on the overarching aims and objectives of the task, the geographical scope of the mapping, and the preliminary list of themes identified for the mapping. In line with the resolutions of the workshop, the geographical scope of Task 3.1 has been limited to the EU Member States represented by the REBOOT Consortium.

The workshop comprising Milestone 3 has been consolidated into a blog post by SSSA and was published on the REBOOT project's website on 20.03.2023. For further information on the blog post, please visit: <https://thereboot-project.eu/blog/blogpost-0003>

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7. MILESTONE 4 – 1ST WAVE OUTCOMES UNIVIE (M12): 1ST INTERIM CONFERENCE & PROGRESS REPORTS

On February 7, 2024, the University of Vienna (UNIVIE) as coordinator of the project organised the first wave outcomes meeting as part of the project's milestones. Held online from 10:00 am to 12:00 pm CET, the meeting incorporated the 1st interim conference and progress reports from all partners, under the direction of the project coordinator. This structured, two-hour conference provided a comprehensive platform for all partners to present their progress, achievements, and deliverables.

The agenda included updates on work in progress, deliverables, in-scope and out-of-scope activities, and an overall overview of the project. Representatives from each partner institution attended and contributed to the discussion. Participants included:

UNIVIE: Katharine Sarikakis, Angeliki Chatziefrimidou, Janina Juengst, Gentiana Ramadani

UCM: Fernando Ramos, Loreto Corredoira, Laura Caballero

ELIAMEP: Anna Kandyla, Alexia Mitsikostas, Laia Comerma Calatayud, Irene Andriopoulou, Eirini Sifaki

ULIEGE: Antonios Vlassis

KHAS: Melis Behlil, Elif Akcali, Ruken Erdede

SSSA: Caterina Sganga, Denise Amram, Pelin Turan, Arianna Martinelli, Piergiorgio Pilo

UGENT: Daniel Biltreyst, Engelart Willems

UC3M: Trinidad Garcia Leiva, Isabela Miranda

UCA: Jean-François Trubert, Marcin Sobieszczanski, Julie Mansion-Vaquie

EUR: Mafalda Damaso

JYU: Tuuli Lähdesmäki, Kaisa Hiltunen

UW: Michał Głowacki, Jacek Mikucki

Participants and speakers focused specifically on the project's progress to date, bringing to discussion the review and findings on competitiveness in the European film industry. Some of the presented and discussed themes included:

- Evaluation of the EU's approaches to promoting the 'competitiveness' of the audiovisual sector and the European film industry, considering technological changes over the years.
- International perspectives on what defines 'European' in the European film industry.

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- Case study data exploring how the European Film Academy works to enhance the future competitiveness of the European film industry by engaging young audiences through the Young Audience Award (YAA).
 - Socio-economic indicators mapping of the movie industry in Europe.

Each work package leader presented their work in collaboration with the partners who contributed to each task and deliverable. This was done through a PowerPoint template, which provided a structured and visually coherent overview of the contributions from all parties involved. Each working package was thoroughly explained, highlighting the roles and responsibilities of the lead partner as well as the specific contributions made by each partner regarding the progress of the work done so far. By using a standardised template, the presentation maintained consistency and ensured that the key points of each working package were communicated effectively.

WP1 Project Management – (UNIVIE)

The project management and administration for WP1 have been carried out in a collaborative and highly coordinated manner, ensuring smooth progress and adherence to deadlines. At the first wave outcomes regarding the milestone number 4, 12 deliverables were submitted successfully according to the established timelines. Looking ahead, 10 more deliverables were planned for submission in 2024.

Communication and coordination between all partners have been at the forefront of the project's goal. From the very beginning, effective channels for information exchange were established, allowing for regular updates and swift resolution of any issues that arose. This open line of communication ensured that all partners remained aligned with the project's objectives and that any challenges could be addressed in a timely manner.

University of Vienna as coordinator took care of the whole process of the preparation and submission of all deliverables including here the designation of official templates deliverables, blog posts, and policy briefs.

To engage with the wider community and keep stakeholders informed, a social media presence was developed early in the project. A concrete media plan was created to ensure that posts were regularly shared, highlighting key achievements and updates.

The project's website has been another key communication tool, regularly updated with new information about the project's milestones, deliverables, and any amendments. This ensured that

all stakeholders, including partners and external audiences, can easily access up-to-date details on the project's progress.

The coordinator has also handled any necessary amendments or changes to the project scope time after time as per the project's needs. Overall, the management and administration of WP1 have been characterised by strong communication, effective use of resources, and a collaborative spirit among all partners. The established systems for internal management, media engagement, and project communication have contributed to a good delivery of milestones and ensure that the project will continue to progress smoothly toward its next set of goals.

WP2 Diachronic understandings of the 'competitiveness' and of the 'European' in EFI (UCM)

The presentation covered two areas: it referred firstly to a deliverable that at the time had just been completed (D2.1) and then informed about the work done in the two other tasks of the work package and the deliverables associated with it (D2.2, D2.3 and D2.4)

Task 2.1 The competitiveness of the EFI in EU law and governance: A diachronic analysis, was led by ELIAMEP. It offered a diachronic analysis of the development and evolution of EU action in the film sector, examining the ways in which the EU has approached, defined and sought to promote the 'competitiveness' of the EFI. It also explored whether technological transformations, in particular online platforms, and the COVID-19 pandemic have impacted the EU's definition of what is a 'competitive EFI' and juxtaposes EU policy approaches to a 'competitive EFI' with the work of the Council of Europe (CoE) in this field.

This task produced D2.1 (Competitiveness in European law), which was due in month 12 (January 2024) and was carried out as expected. The research team involved in this task began working on it in month 1 (February 2023) and submitted the deliverable before its deadline. The task involved researchers from ELIAMEP and ULIEGE, which collaborated in order to perform the analysis and obtain the results outlined in the deliverable. The team had monthly meetings in order to evaluate the progress of the research, and to discuss the objectives and work plan for the next period. The frequency of meetings increased as the deliverable deadline approached. The work was distributed in a fairly balanced way between the two participants, while ELIAMEP also took the necessary coordinating work as the task leader.

D2.1 builds on an in-depth diachronic textual analysis of legislative and non-legislative acts and policy instruments issued by the EU institutions, covering a period of more than 40 years, and involve in particular 183 documents published by the European Commission, the European

Parliament, the Council, and the European Parliament and the Council as co-legislators, along with a selection of documents issued by the Council of Europe (CoE). Given the significant number of documents under study and the long historical period under examination, the research question guiding the analysis is approached from various perspectives. As such, the study combines quantitative and qualitative methods of textual analysis, which enhance each other. The quantitative textual mapping performed seeks to shed light on the diachronic use of the term 'competitiveness' in the European audiovisual policy framework, and to understand the ways in which 'competitiveness' has historically been understood in the light of other key terms, concepts, and principles of European audiovisual and film governance. The qualitative analysis performed examines the most significant EU legal instruments relating to regulation and financial support, as well as a selected set of EU policy documents regarding the audiovisual sector and the EFI.

The report demonstrates that the understanding of 'competitiveness' in EU legislative and non-legislative acts and documents has evolved with the times, reflecting the challenges of a changing reality in which the emergence of new technologies and globalisation have shaken the audiovisual sector to its core. This is also the case with the concept of 'cultural diversity', which has similarly imbued EU action targeting the audiovisual sector and the EFI. The documents analysed show that cultural diversity has been perceived from multiple perspectives and that it has become interlinked over time with the competitiveness of the audiovisual industry and the EFI, reflecting the complexity but also the breadth and potential of the two concepts as a key asset for policymaking regarding the audiovisual sector and the EFI.

Overall, D2.1 shows that the concept of 'competitiveness' is of a multifaceted nature, which results in intricate synergies when it is employed concurrently with the concept of 'cultural diversity'. This is reflected in the regulatory framework established, the funding instruments enacted, and the policy approaches followed by the EU, which on the whole display an increasingly sophisticated understanding of 'competitiveness' and 'cultural diversity'. Building on the results of D2.1, the book *"Values and principles in EU cultural governance: The quest for fairness, diversity and competitiveness"* (tentative title) will bring together the findings from the REBOOT project and the findings from another Horizon Europe-funded project in which the ELIAMEP and ULIEGE teams are involved (FAIRMUSE: <https://fairmuse.eu/>). An open access publishing contract was signed with Routledge.

During this first period significant preparation took place for the dissemination of the T2.1 findings. The other four teams working in this WP kept working in their own individual lines of research and

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in coordination. They prepared three deliverables and one policy brief due in month 24 of the project.

WP3 The institutional context of the EU film industry – (ELIAMEP)

The general objective of WP3 is to explore the distinct laws and policies governing the European Film Industry (EFI) and its presence on the international scene, their contribution to the competitiveness of the sector and EU values, as well as practices and institutions shaping a regularising environment for filmmaking. It involves two work streams: one on the laws and policies governing the EFI in the EU; and another devoted to the laws and policies governing the presence of the EFI on the international scene, both examining the support for competitiveness and cultural diversity. The first work stream is composed of three tasks, whose cumulative objective is to map the filmmaking regulatory framework in the EU, analyse the main EU initiatives to promote the EFI, and study the way in which lived practice and experience, as well as the internal and other regulatory arrangements of public institutions conduct a regulatory environment for the promotion of European filmmaking and consumption. The second work stream is again composed of three tasks, which aim to analyse the institutional and policy models across EU Member States for the promotion of the EFI at the international level, explore the EU's legislative and governance framework and its promotion of the EFI on the international scene, and analyse the role of EU delegations in promoting the EFI.

T3.2 Analysis of EU initiative promoting the EFI: The case of LUX Audience Award (JYU)

Work has been completed. The analysis is included in D3.1 which is in a finalisation process.

Key Findings:

In this study, the competitiveness of the LUX scheme was examined based on various economic and non-economic indicators. The results showed that the indicators examined, namely revenues, admissions, countries of release, awards, professional criticism, newspaper journalism, online criticism, and online ratings by critics, are significantly correlated with each other. An increase in one of the indicators is likely to lead to an increase in the others. While the study suggests such a correlation, the statistics of these indicators and their comparison with the European winners of the much more prestigious film awards, the Palme d'Or and the Oscar for the Best Foreign Film, show that the LUX winners are not very competitive in the global or even European film scene. In fact, some of the films have very low admissions and are not widely distributed or recognised by film

critics and newspapers. Although LUX winners have rarely been transnational box office successes, they have received numerous awards at major film festivals. Examination of LUX award-winning films shows that they tend to be contemporary dramas dealing with serious social and societal issues. In this study, we also examined the evolution of the competitiveness of the LUX scheme by comparing the winners before and after the change of the scheme from a prize selected by MEPs to an audience award combining both MEPs and audience voting. The results show that the change of the scheme did not have a major impact on its competitiveness indicators nor on the content or style of the winning films.

Task T3.3: Lived practices, principles, cultural institutions, and the ‘fringes’ of filmmaking and consumption (M6-M27), under WP3 (UNIVIE): The institutional context of the EU film industry. Work in progress.

As the leading partner, UNIVIE, in collaboration with UGENT, is examining how lived practices, institutional arrangements, and public service media (PSM) frameworks foster a regulatory environment that promotes European filmmaking and consumption.

The research spans six EU countries-Austria, Belgium, Greece, Spain, France, and Poland-and investigates the dynamics surrounding the training, development, and promotion of films that exist on the fringes of the core film sector. This includes alternative filmmaking, fictional and factual works, which document and challenge existing narratives around diversity and democracy. Special attention is given to supporting cross-sectional storytelling by youth, women, and migrants. The methodology involves desk research on trends, policies, and historical practices in alternative filmmaking, as well as interviews with stakeholders in the focus countries. As part of T3.3, significant progress in disseminating its findings was made:

Chapter Publication (WP3 - Fringes): *And... Action! The Politics of Youth Collectives Shaping Documentary Filmmaking in Europe*. Published in *The Bloomsbury Handbook of Global Documentary and Cinematic Storytelling (2025)* by Katharine Sarikakis, Gentiana Ramadani, and Janina Juengst.

Task 3.4 Promotion of the EFI at the international level: Institutional and policy models across the EU Member States

T3.4 started at month 6 and so far, the T3.4 team which involves several consortium partners, has organised four online collective meetings with attendance from all partners. The T3.4 team co-designed the script of a common semi-structured interview, which will be carried out with key

informants across public authorities and relevant stakeholders in France, Spain, Italy, Greece, Poland and the Nordic countries of Finland, Sweden, and Denmark. This script was tested with institutional actors in Finland by JYU and based on this experience, it was subsequently edited by the T3.4 team. JYU has begun to do exploratory interviews. All the partners involved in the task (ULIEGE, ELIAMEP, EUR, JYU, UC3M, SSSA, UWARSAW) plan to carry out their interviews between February and July 2024. All partners have produced a list of relevant stakeholders involved in the international promotion of the national film sector in the selected countries and they have identified the main contacts that they will interview. The interviews will follow the same structure: profile, institutional promotion (general), institutional promotion and the international market, institutional promotion and relationship with stakeholders, institutional promotion and power relationships, institutional promotion and streaming platforms, institutional promotion and COVID-19. The results of the interviews will be triangulated with policy documents associated with the practices for the international promotion of the film sector in the selected EU MSs. The partners involved in the task have gathered most of such data and policy documents. They have also developed literature reviews focused on their specific countries. Finally, the T3.4 team co-designed the common structure of the comparative study, which will be based on the following aspects: Objectives of the policies of each Member State dealing with the international promotion of the film sector; Mapping of the key institutional-policy actors involved in the international promotion of the film sector and their role; Programs/support schemes/cooperative arrangements to promote the national film industry internationally (with a focus on different cinematographic works and on the link between national policies and European cooperative arrangements-EURIMAGES, MEDIA MUNDUS); National policy practices and streaming services; National policy practices and COVID-19 pandemic.

ELIAMEP presented **the work of T3.5 (EU law and governance and the promotion of the EFI on the international scene) which it is leading**. T3.5 started in month 1 (February 2023) and will be completed by month 30 (July 2025). It focuses on the laws and policies governing the presence of the European film sector on the international scene and seeks to assess whether, and if so how, EU law and policy promotes the EFI on the international scene. ELIAMEP presented its research design, focusing on the various available instruments it has identified, namely economic and other agreements concluded by the EU with third countries and funding instruments targeting the internationalisation of the EU film industry, and on which the research will be based. ELIAMEP's team had also assembled a corpus of relevant literature dealing with EU law and film policies at

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the international level. The next steps involve analysing the available instruments and developing interview guides for interviewing high-level officials from the EU institutions and selected umbrella organisations of cultural stakeholders at the EU level. As for the other consortium teams participating in this task, it has been agreed in joint meetings that the SSSA team will analyse patterns of cultural cooperation between the EU and the CoE as well as between the EU and the UN, while UNIVIE will examine the gender dimension of the EU development cooperation policy.

T3.6 Analysis of EU delegations' role in promoting the EFI: The case of the EU Film Festivals (JYU)

Research has been completed, but since T3.2 has been integrated with T3.6, the deliverable is in finalisation process for D3.1 "Report on the Lux Audience Award & European film Festivals (JYU, M32)". Goals for the next 6 months: finalising the deliverable; sending it to internal review; and making the needed revisions based on review comments.

Key Findings:

The EUFF is characterised by a complex organisational structure involving both high-level official actors and local film festival organisations and associations, which usually take on the practical organisational responsibilities and compensate for the lack of film expertise in the EU delegation and the embassies and other representations of the EU Member States. This organisational structure is also reflected in the curatorial challenges of the festival. In line with the EU's objectives, the discourses of the festival programmes typically emphasise European values such as democracy, freedom, equality, human rights and diversity. Alongside the films and the festival discourses, the side events support such an agenda. Side events are typically based on one-way exchanges. The organisation of EUFFs is a balancing act between different objectives. This balancing act seeks to combine the rationales of supporting the film industry and using film for diverse social and societal activities, such as strengthening intercultural dialogue and international cultural relations. The analysis revealed the ambiguity of the diplomatic discourses and practices involved in the EUFF: This top-down approach is in line with traditional cultural diplomacy. On the other hand, the EUFF involves a strong people-to-people approach to diplomacy. The analysis of the seven films that either had the most screenings at the case EUFFs or were among the most requested films from the film repository showed that EUFF films are audience-friendly dramas or drama comedies that deal with even serious themes in an uplifting and hopeful manner. The films do not include any disturbing content such as explicit violence or sex.

WP4 The framings and strategies of cinema professionals (ULIEGE)

Task 4.1 officially commenced in Month 4 (May 2023) of the project and will be completed in month 30 (July 2025). This aligns with deliverables D4.1 Report on perspectives of “international market” from EFI. The activities for this task have been systematically implemented and are still in progress by staying true to the project’s timeline and the specified methodology to achieve the outlined objectives.

The work carried out within this task is divided into two phases: desk research and data collection. In the initial stage, emphasis was placed on desk research, involving an extensive literature review and the gathering and examination of grey literature from various associations within the film industry, alongside compiling a contact list. This foundational work set the stage for the subsequent phase of data collection.

Literature Review: The comprehensive literature review involved collecting and analysing materials on cross-cutting topics essential for understanding the European Film Industry's (EFI) positioning in the international market. The mapping encompassed competition in film industries and the tensions to ensure a balance between economic and cultural ambitions, the dynamics of the international film market.

At the European level, the primary focus of investigation revolves around discerning the priorities of film professionals and their pivotal role in shaping internationalisation strategies for the European Film Industry. A central theme in this exploration is the examination of co-productions – a key determinant in understanding the role of funding mechanisms and co-production schemes, along with their tangible impact on content creation and its potential for internationalisation. Given the significance of the UK in attaining international market exposure through co-productions it is possible that Brexit generates tensions in relation to the co-production landscape involving the UK. In addition, the Task 4.1 underscores the need for a nuanced analysis of the differences between co-productions within the European Union and those outside its borders, offering valuable insights into the potentials and challenges inherent in these collaborative endeavors.

Another critical facet at the EU level pertains to the role of public service media in supporting the EFI. Despite being indispensable partners, these broadcasters encounter challenges such as fragmentation and heightened competition with emerging Video on Demand (VoD) services. A pivotal aspect of Task 4.1 is the identification of EFI's primary competitors and the exploration of potential key partners. This analysis is poised to provide strategic direction for EFI in navigating

the complex global film market. Turning attention to the international market beyond the EU, the Task 4.1 raises critical questions about the role of VoD platforms in shaping distribution channels and retaining intellectual property (IP). The exploration aims to unravel perceptions regarding the influence of VoD platforms on content creation, the impact of the Audiovisual Media Services Directive (AVMSD) on EFI competitiveness, and the intensifying competition between EU-based and US-based VoD platforms.

The insights gained from the literature review were instrumental in identifying key areas of investigation, ensuring that the questionnaire would effectively capture the diverse perspectives and concerns of stakeholders within the music industry.

Grey Literature Analysis: Gray literature from eight key European associations, including the Federation of European Screen Directors, EUROCINEMA, Europa Distribution, and other associations (Europa International, European Film Promotion, etc.), was meticulously collected and analysed. This rich source of information provided additional perspectives, contributing to a more nuanced understanding of the EFI landscape.

Questionnaire Development: Building on insights from the literature review and grey literature, the questionnaire was crafted to explore central tensions and challenges faced by the EFI in the international market. The questionnaire comprises 54 questions across 11 sub-sections, covering aspects such as general EFI values and challenges, perceptions on competitiveness, the impact of the increasing presence of VoD platforms, the role of public broadcasters in increasing EFI competitiveness, exploring the strengths and needs of the existent institutional context in supporting EFI internationalisation, the role of international co-productions, understandings of European cinema identity, identification on the international competitors, and the impact of COVID-19. The questionnaire was revised by our partner Mafalda Damaso of Erasmus Universiteit Rotterdam, and after integrating her feedback we refined the questionnaire to 20 mandatory questions aligned with the research goals.

Survey Development: To assess professionals' understanding at the national level, an online panel survey was adapted from the questionnaire, presenting a more direct style with multiple-choice and ranking options. The survey, reviewed by Mafalda Damaso-EUR, comprises four sections and 32 questions, aligning with the research objectives. All partners involved in the T4.1 have already sent their feedback on the questionnaire and they are committed to

disseminate the survey towards their national and local networks. The survey is currently being integrated in Qualtrics and its dissemination is expected to take place in Month 16.

List of Contacts: ULIEGE conducted an extensive mapping of relevant associations and professionals, resulting in a developing list of 78 contacts from 37 organisations. The contact list includes a mix of professional associations and public and private institutions. The list is dynamic and continually evolving based on ongoing interviews and recommendations.

Conducting Interviews: ULIEGE developed an e-mail template presenting the REBOOT project and the goals of T.4.1 to invite the interviewees from the contact list. Additionally, a consent form allowing different levels of disclosure was elaborated. Initiated in early December, contacting potential interviewees identified in the comprehensive list of contacts is underway.

The interview started in January and are still ongoing. As of now, a total of five interviews have been conducted, and four are scheduled to take place in the following months. The interviews are conducted as semi-structured sessions in English, accommodating both in-person and online formats, with each session lasting approximately one hour. Following these discussions, transcripts are produced and refined for clarity and coherence. This preparatory work sets the stage for a detailed analysis in the subsequent phase of the research.

The interviews encompass diverse stakeholders within the film industry, going beyond the initially planned eight European associations. The interviews conducted so far encompass representatives of the European Film Promotion, Europe International, European VOD Coalition, EUROCINEMA, International Union of Cinemas.

Finally, the ULIEGE team wrote a chapter related to preliminary results from the T4.1 that will be included in the book edited by several REBOOT partners.

Task 4.2 officially commenced in Month 1 (February 2023) of the project timeline, and it will be completed in Month 30 (July 2025). As indicated within the Grant Agreement, this task is closely connected to Task 3.1, which is organised under WP3 and is dedicated to the mapping of the regulatory framework that informs and governs the film-making industry. Accordingly, the activities to be performed throughout this task are synchronised with the research activities planned in the context of Task 3.1, and the research outcomes are planned to be delivered in

three stages vis-à-vis the project timeline, the goals of the task and the methodology adopted to achieve this goal.

The ultimate goal of Task 4.2 is to produce an up-to-date and more extensive version of the sets of codes of best practices (please see: CoBP for immersive experiences and CoBP for documentary filmmakers) previously produced by the H2020 reCreating Europe project.

To fulfil this task, an eclectic methodology bringing together desk-based doctrinal research and empirical research has been embraced. To collect data, the research team relies, primarily, on systematic literature review and mapping of public regulatory sources (e.g. legislation and case law). These practices are aimed at, firstly, to contemplate the legal hurdles faced by specific cinema professionals (i.e. makers of short movies, documentaries, arthouse movies, as well as the players involved in the making of movies produced by marginalised groups or in minority languages) and to identify the legal tools that may facilitate or hinder their professional practices as such. Accordingly, the first stage of Task 4.2 (Months 1-12) is allocated to data collection via desk-based research, mainly by adopting systematic and thematic literature review, on the one hand, and systematic mapping of public regulatory sources, on the other.

As a first step of this stage, research has been conducted by utilising open- and closed-access databases that are available to the partner institution (SSSA) via analogue and digital means. This practice proved crucial in terms of identifying the secondary sources of law (e.g. EU-funded studies, books, book chapters, journal articles, documents produced by international and regional organisations, online sources) that helped set the theoretical backbone of the research and to identify the issues encountered by the aforementioned cinema professionals. The key findings of this research endeavour have been consolidated into a working document (WD) which clusters the complications that copyright law causes to the EFI, by taking into account the five main phases of the film-making process (i.e. pre- and post-production, dissemination, exhibition in traditional and alternative platforms, preservation) and the struggles of the stakeholders involved in each phase thereof.

Building upon the findings of the literature review, the focus of the research activities shifted to find out and catalogue the primary sources of law (e.g. EU Directives and Regulations, CJEU case law, national legislation, national case law, if possible) that are relevant to analyse and

interpret the issues indicated in the scholarship. This list, primarily focusing on the EU legislative framework, has been expanded with the international and regional legal instruments administered by the UN and its specialised agencies, such as WIPO and UNESCO, WTO as well as the Council of Europe (CoE), with the aim of providing legal basis to matters that have not been covered in the EU legal framework (e.g. definition of works that entail copyright protection, eligibility criteria for copyright protection, rules governing authorship of works, including the joint-authorship of works as such). Having consolidated into another WD, this list consists of the legal instruments to be systematically analysed by the research team. The mapping of copyright-related instruments administered by UN, UNESCO, WIPO and WTO instruments has been completed, whereas the mapping of the national legislative frameworks of the selected EU Member States is in progress.

Taking the legal tools that are related to the EFI, either by enabling or disabling the access to, (re) use and dissemination of in-copyright and out-of-copyright elements by the key players of the EFI; the mapping activities have been organised in five Excel sheets (i.e. fundamentals of copyright, term of legal protection, copyright exceptions and limitations, public domain and other facilitated uses of works, licensing schemes), each of which consists of 12 pages dedicated to the international instruments (i.e. UN, UNESCO, WIPO, WTO), regional tools (i.e. CoE), and the selected EU Member States (i.e. Austria, Belgium, Finland, France, Greece, Italy, the Netherlands, Poland, Spain). To further collect data, survey questions are to be administered to the experts in the field in the selected EU Member States. The research team has compiled a pool of survey questions on diverse topics. The questions are to be refined and communicated to the experts in the second stage (Months 13-24) of the project as well.

Finally, at the third stage of the research (Months 24-30), the research team will pursue their research endeavours with data analysis, while triangulating the data collected by desk-based research against formal deliberative exercises to be performed with key stakeholders of the EFI. Therefore, the research team will, first, draft a set of codes of best practices, which will be opened to discussion at a workshop to be organised with the participation of a wide spectrum of key stakeholders. After testing the efficiency of the codes with the prospective participants of the workshop, the research team will edit, if necessary, the codes and will produce the final version of the codes of best practices.

T4.3 team has co-designed the script of a common semi-structured interview, which will be carried out with key informants across the film supply chains in the selected international film markets. This script was tested with film professionals by the UC3M partner and based on this experience, it was subsequently edited by the T4.3 team. The completed questionnaire consists of 12 questions, organised into various topics, including personal background, perceptions of the European Film Industry (EFI), distribution practices, co-production, film festivals, and geopolitical considerations regarding collaboration with international players such as Hollywood majors and Chinese or Indian support programs.

Interviews have begun to be organised and carried out by the collaborating partners. Specifically, UC3M has already successfully completed interviews in Argentina. The remaining partners involved in the task will start their interviews by mid-2024. All partners have identified the main contacts that they will interview in their markets.

Alongside the ongoing interview activities, an online panel survey is being developed to extend the outreach to a broader spectrum of film professionals within the targeted international markets. This survey has been refined from the original questionnaire to offer a more succinct format, incorporating multiple-choice and ranking questions. This approach is anticipated to facilitate the collection of a richer set of data, encompassing both quantitative and qualitative insights, thereby enhancing the research findings.

The results of the interviews and the survey will be triangulated with market data and policy documents associated with the local film sectors. The partners involved in the task have gathered most of such data and policy documents. They have also developed literature reviews focused on their specific international markets.

Task 4.3 supports REBOOT's bottom-up examination of the characteristics, strengths, needs and opportunities of the European Film Industry across the supply chain, both on its own and vis-à-vis its main competitors (USA, China, India). The resulting analysis will foreground the industrial and geopolitical particularities of the EFI from an international and industrial perspective. Based on this knowledge, REBOOT's partners will be able to make recommendations to increase the competitiveness of the EFI in the international arena and to

suggest avenues to strengthen cultural diversity within the international film market itself. To ensure success, further research is needed.

Finally, the T4.3 team co-wrote an abstract for a chapter that will be included in the book edited by several REBOOT partners.

WP5 Building the future competitiveness (UNIVIE)

WP5 focuses on investigating and predicting future trends to enhance the competitiveness of the European Film Industry (EFI). This work package addresses multiple dimensions, including creativity, skills development, production processes, audience preferences, and innovative content interaction. A key focus is placed on an underexplored aspect of filmmaking: music as an innovation, alongside cultural and educational elements. WP5 also explores policy and ethical implications, particularly concerning the protection of children's well-being and rights in the industry.

The deliverables under WP5, which present findings in respective reports, include:

T5.1 Analysis of Young People's Film Preferences in Europe: The Case Study of the Young Audience Award (JYU).

The work contributed to a report on the report on EU young audience award. Task completed. Research commenced in February 2023 with the planning of the study. Desktop analysis and film reviews were conducted in March and April 2023. Interviews with representatives from the European Film Academy and an online meeting took place in March, April, and June. The deliverable was drafted in April and May, underwent internal review in May, and was finalised and proofread in June. A comprehensive analysis was conducted, which included interviews with representatives from the European Film Academy. This effort aimed to gather insights into current trends and perspectives shaping the European film landscape. It was found that the 12–14-year-old jury members appreciate films with substantial themes. The Youth Academy Awards show great promise in promoting film literacy among young people in Europe and beyond, combining a youth film competition with educational objectives.

T5.2: Survey on young people's film preferences in Europe (JYU)

Task focuses on the survey on young people's film preferences in Europe covering the design, completion, and implementation is ongoing.

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T5.3 The cognitive skills developed in the creation and reception of content in Mixed Reality includes two other subtasks; “Study of the cognitive abilities of young content creators in Mixed Reality” and “The experimental study of the reception practices of content in Mixed Reality by young audiences” (UCA). To explore the impact of new audiovisual technologies on young audiences, this task draws on an experiment study with students in two master’s programs, all in all around 50 people. The team organised both, viewing sessions of different immersive videos and other VR products, on two types of equipment.

T5.4 The comparative studies on creative production process for film music in Europe which includes the sub task of understanding processes, options and decision making, examines the creative process in music for visual media through a practical case study. At each stage of the production process, the strategies developed by the composers to optimise production time and costs without degrading aesthetic quality are highlighted. The final report has provided replicable capacities for future competitiveness in film music production and is based on comparative studies of the creative production process for film music in Europe. Through a practical case study, it examined decision-making processes and strategies used by composers to optimise production time and costs while maintaining high aesthetic standards.

T5.5 Teenagers and Youth: tastes and interactions regarding transnational and European filmic content (UNIVIE), has a strong research focus on engaging teenagers and young adults by analysing their tastes and interactions with transnational and European film content. The focus group questionnaire has been finalised, after the conduction of the pilot test, meeting dates have been scheduled, and registration for the 18-24 age group has closed with 30 participants registered.

WP6 – Indicators and recommendations SSSA

WP6 focuses on socio-economic indicators and recommendations related to EFI. To achieve this, the WP is divided into three tasks, led by SSSA (ECON team).

The first task, **T6.1 (M4-M28) - The socio-economic status of the movie industry in Europe: quantitative mapping and related indicators** (Lead Partner: SSSA; UNIVIE), is further divided into two subtasks:

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ST6.1.1 – Quantitative mapping of the movie industry in the EU economy:

The results of this subtask were presented during the first internal REBOOT Conference in Cannes and submitted as **Deliverable D6.1 - Report on the Indicators (M16)**. The presentation included a general overview of the state of the art, methodological notes, and preliminary results. The final outcomes will also be integrated into the **Competitiveness Dashboard** under Task 6.2.

ST6.1.2 – Mapping EU movie industry content into SDGs:

This sub-task was presented as ongoing work during the first internal REBOOT Conference in Cannes, where an abstract of the work was provided. The final outcomes will be incorporated into the **Competitiveness Dashboard** under Task 6.2 (M34).

The second task, **T6.2 (M28-M34) - Devising a Film Industry Competitiveness Dashboard** (Lead Partner: SSSA; UNIVIE, UCM, UGENT, UW, UCA), was mentioned during the presentation, with a note that it will commence at M28.

The third task, **T6.3 (M28-M36) - Integrated policy recommendations and "A Policy Agenda for EU Film 2030"** (Lead Partner: SSSA; UNIVIE, EUR, ELIAMEP, ULIEGE, UCA, JYU), was also mentioned during the presentation, confirming that it will start at M28.

Additionally, the intervention outlined the timeline for each task, providing a broader overview of the ongoing work and upcoming activities of the SSSA–ECON team to raise awareness. Following the presentation, some interventions and questions were raised, primarily concerning the role of the Competitiveness Dashboard, including privacy-related issues.

In terms of WP7 – Dissemination, a total of 4 deliverables were submitted successfully according to the established timelines in this work package. These deliverables represent a comprehensive approach to ensuring the visibility, accessibility, and impact of the project's outcomes across various platforms and audiences.

D7.1 – Website for the Work of the Consortium

A centralised platform has been developed to showcase the consortium's activities, updates, and deliverables, ensuring transparency and accessibility for stakeholders and the general public. And a newsletter section is part of it.

D7.3 – Press Publicity of Commencement

A coordinated press campaign was conducted to announce the commencement of the project, generating initial awareness and engagement across multiple communication channels.

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D7.5 – Scientific Publications: Open Access

Peer-reviewed open-access publication is produced to disseminate the research findings to the academic community and beyond, ensuring widespread accessibility and adherence to open science principles. Work still in progress.

D7.6 – Policy Briefings Derived from WP2–WP5

Policy briefs summarising key insights and recommendations from the research conducted in WP2 to WP5 were prepared to inform and guide decision-makers. All policy briefs are published on the Reboot website. During the reporting period, (February 2023-January 2024) 10 blog posts were published on the website.

Publications

Book Chapters

- **E. Psychogiopoulou, A. Samaras, L. Comerma** – EU Law and the Competitiveness of the Audiovisual Sector and the European Film Industry: The Trajectory of an Evolving Concept (Forthcoming, Palgrave)
- **Caterina Sganga & Pelin Turan** – A Panoptic View of the Common European Data Space for Cultural Heritage Through the Lens of the European Film Industry.
- **Mafalda Dâmaso et al.** – Mapping the European Film Industry in the Argentinian, Brazilian, Mexican, South African, South Korean, and Turkish Markets: Roles, Trends, and Gaps
- **Kaisa Hiltunen & Tuuli Lähdesmäki** – The Young Audience Award: Cultivating Future Audiences for European Cinema (Forthcoming, Palgrave).
- **Tuuli Lähdesmäki & Kaisa Hiltunen** – Governing the European Film Industry by Prizes: The European Film Awards and the LUX European Audience Film Award.(Forthcoming, Palgrave).
- **Edited Book** (Forthcoming, Palgrave)
- **Katharine Sarikakis, Antonios Vlassis & Tuuli Lähdesmäki** (Eds.) – Introduction: The Governance of Competitiveness in the European Film Industry.
- **Katharine Sarikakis, Angeliki Chatziefrimidou, Janina Jüngst, and Gentiana Ramadani** –Young People and the European Film Industry: The Governance of “Near Misses” (Forthcoming, Palgrave).
- **Katharine Sarikakis, Gentiana Ramadani, and Janina Jüngst** – And... Action! The Politics of Youth Collectives Shaping Documentary Filmmaking in Europe – The

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Bloomsbury Handbook of Global Documentary and Cinematic Storytelling (Forthcoming, Bloomsbury).

Journal Articles

- **Biltreyest, D., Gipponi, E., & Miconi, A.** (Eds.). (2023) Cinematic Continuities, Changes and Challenges in Europe: Reflections on Recent Shifts in European Cinema. Theme issue for: *Cinéma & Cie: Film and Media Studies Journal*, 23(41): 1-211. <https://riviste.unimi.it/index.php/cinemaetcie/>
- **Kaisa Hiltunen & Tuuli Lähdesmäki** – Young Audience Award ja eurooppalaisen nuorten elokuvan edistäminen [Young Audience Award and Promoting European Youth Film]. (Forthcoming in 2025, accepted, Kulttuurintutkimus)
- **Denise Amram & Nicoletta Patti** – Recent Policy Initiatives and Safeguards for Children as Online Users (Paper ID 2402). Accepted at IDC 2024: Designing for Children's Rights and Digital Wellbeing: An Agenda for Research and Practice, Delft, The Netherlands. <https://idc.acm.org/2024/>

Conferences (scheduled at the time of reporting-February 6, 2024):

- **April 2024** – Media Industries 2024, King's College London
Presentation: "Towards a European Model of International Film Competitiveness: Comparing Existing Indicators with the Views of European Professionals"
Panel: I8 -Assessing Competitiveness in European Film Industries
Co-authors: Antonios Vlassis, Katharine Sarikakis, and Marina Rossato Fernandes
- **June 19-21, 2024** – 12th Biennial Conference of the SGEU, Universidade NOVA, Lisbon
Confirmed participation of Evangelia Psychogiopoulou and Anna Kandyla
Presentation: "Trade, Development, and the Cultural Sector: An Impossible Nexus?"
- **September 2024** – San Sebastian International Film Festival (SSIFF)
Apostolos Samaras will present Reboot WP2
Presentation of main results of D2.1 and the relevant policy brief, in collaboration with Antonios Vlassis (ULiège)
- **September 2024** – 10th European Communication Conference (ECREA 2024): Communication & Social (Dis)Order
Presentation: "Young People and the European Film Industry: The Governance of 'Near Misses'" (Forthcoming, Palgrave)

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Co-authors: Katharine Sarikakis, Gentiana Ramadani & Janina Jüngst

Presenters: Gentiana Ramadani & Janina Jüngst

Presentations

- **19 December 2023** – Presentation of the REBOOT project on the European Children's Film Association website.
<https://www.ecfaweb.org/a-new-horizon-research-project/#more-7299>
- **June 2023** – Invited Paper, Closed Seminar, European Parliament
Speaker at a closed roundtable: Policy Directions in EU International Cultural Relations Towards 2024 Organised by Culture Solutions and MEP Salima Yenbou, European Parliament.
- **February 2024** – Expert Committee Contribution, European Parliament
Contribution to the CULT Committee exchange of views on recent developments in the EU's Cultural Diplomacy. European Parliament, Brussels.
https://multimedia.europarl.europa.eu/en/webstreaming/event_20240213-0900-COMMITTEE-CULT?start=240213080547&end=240213113448&audio=en (from 10:00 to 10:10).

Research Talks

- **November 2024** - Seminar of the Finnish Society for Cinema Studies
Presentation: Quantitative analysis of the LUX Prize as a tool for promoting European cinema
Speakers: Kaisa Hiltunen
- **June 2024** – University of Vienna, Department of Communication
Presentation: Governance of Competitiveness in the European Film Industry
Speakers: Gentiana Ramadani & Janina Jüngst
- **November 2023** – Seminar of the Finnish Society for Cinema Studies
Presentation: Young Audience Award and Promoting the Competitiveness of European Cinema
Speakers: Kaisa Hiltunen
- **20 October 2023** – Ghent
Meeting on WP2 and discussion with documentary filmmaker Paul Pauwels.
Speaker/s: Daniël Biltereyst, Fernando Arenas, Engelart Willems, Michal Glowacki, Laura Caballero, Kaisa Hiltunen, Loreto Corredoira

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- **6-7 June 2024 – Madrid**

Research talk on WP2

Speaker/s: Fernando Arenas, Michal Glowacki, Daniël Biltereyst, Engelart Willems, Alicja Waszkiewicz-Raviv, Michal Glowacki, Samia Benaissa

Overview of the Work

ID	Del	Del	Description	Responsible	Start	End	Status
101	Del 1	Del 1	Report on EU policy landscape	UNIVIE	1st Jul 2023		Completed
102	Del 1	Del 1	Report on cognitive experience with VR	UNIVIE	1st Jul 2023		Completed
103	Del 1	Del 1	Report on survey from REBOOT	UNIVIE	1st Jul 2023		Completed
104	Del 1	Del 1	Report on survey from REBOOT	UNIVIE	1st Jul 2023		Completed
105	Del 1	Del 1	Report on survey from REBOOT	UNIVIE	1st Jul 2023		Completed
106	Del 1	Del 1	Report on survey from REBOOT	UNIVIE	1st Jul 2023		Completed
107	Del 1	Del 1	Report on survey from REBOOT	UNIVIE	1st Jul 2023		Completed
108	Del 1	Del 1	Report on survey from REBOOT	UNIVIE	1st Jul 2023		Completed
109	Del 1	Del 1	Report on survey from REBOOT	UNIVIE	1st Jul 2023		Completed
110	Del 1	Del 1	Report on survey from REBOOT	UNIVIE	1st Jul 2023		Completed
111	Del 1	Del 1	Report on survey from REBOOT	UNIVIE	1st Jul 2023		Completed
112	Del 1	Del 1	Report on survey from REBOOT	UNIVIE	1st Jul 2023		Completed
113	Del 1	Del 1	Report on survey from REBOOT	UNIVIE	1st Jul 2023		Completed
114	Del 1	Del 1	Report on survey from REBOOT	UNIVIE	1st Jul 2023		Completed
115	Del 1	Del 1	Report on survey from REBOOT	UNIVIE	1st Jul 2023		Completed
116	Del 1	Del 1	Report on survey from REBOOT	UNIVIE	1st Jul 2023		Completed
117	Del 1	Del 1	Report on survey from REBOOT	UNIVIE	1st Jul 2023		Completed
118	Del 1	Del 1	Report on survey from REBOOT	UNIVIE	1st Jul 2023		Completed
119	Del 1	Del 1	Report on survey from REBOOT	UNIVIE	1st Jul 2023		Completed
120	Del 1	Del 1	Report on survey from REBOOT	UNIVIE	1st Jul 2023		Completed

During the 1st wave outcome – Interim Conference

8. MILESTONE 5 – 2ND WAVE OUTCOMES UNIVIE (M24)

On January 31, 2025, the Interim Conference was held as part of Milestone No. 5: 2nd Wave of Outcomes, with the participation of all Project Committee members. The meeting began at 11:00 AM CET on Zoom.

Katharine Sarikakis (UNIVIE), as the Project Coordinator, welcomed the partners to the 2nd Interim Conference and presented the agenda. She provided an overview of the meeting’s purpose, emphasising its academic research-oriented nature, which focused on evaluating research progress—a key component of the Grant Agreement.

Following the introduction, Gentiana Ramadani, Project Manager and Researcher of Reboot (UnVie), presented WP1, providing a summary of activities since the last Interim Conference and highlighting the milestones achieved from February 2024 to January 2025.

While assessing the deliverable submissions, she referenced the EU Commission’s review process recommendation from July 2024, which suggested the formalization of a clear review process for all deliverables. This recommendation led to the creation of a structured template specific to the REBOOT project, which is now used by all partners to ensure consistency and clarity in submissions.

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Following the WP1 presentation, Fernando Ramos (UCM), presented the updates made in WP2 indicating the completion of major deliverables (D2.1-2.4) as well as the participation at the Conference: Frames of Change: Historicizing Recent European Cinema (1990-2025) slated from 21.05.2025 to 22.05.2025, Madrid, Spain. He further pointed out that the dissemination tasks for WP2 start this year as the first two years of the grant agreement mainly centered on information collection and research.

Laia Comerma (ELIAMEP) proceeded to synthesise the work progress made in WP3. Giving the floor to Caterina Sganga (SSSA) for T3.1 - “EU and Comparative Legal Mapping of the Regulatory Filmmaking Framework”, she indicated that the data analysis is to be completed by April 2025 with the deadlines being; Internal review of D3.1 (May 2025) & submission to the FTP (June 2025). Following the update, Pelin Turan (SSSA) stressed that the creation of the comprehensive public database to serve as deliverable D3.6 required the collaboration of partners, indicating the availability of completed works on the excel sheet on the consortium’s google drive for further consultation. In addition, Evangelia Psychogiopoulou (ELIAMEP) pointed out the need for coordination of the database’s creation in light of the advances in research to ensure content harmonisation of the database. In response, Katharine Sarikakis indicated that measures will be taken in concertation with the Web design partners to fully grasp the technical aspects of the new feature and further meetings shall ensue to facilitate the process.

This was followed by the presentation of WP4 on framings and strategies of cinema professionals by Antonios Vlassis (ULIEGE), highlighting work progress and key findings of T4.1. The data analysis for task T4.2 currently in progress is expected to be completed in July 2025 and in June 2025 for T4.3. The respective dissemination efforts were also shared.

After a short break, Angeliki Chatziefrimidou (UNIVIE) presented WP5 - “Building the Future Competitiveness” work progress highlighting each team’s progress and deadline slated for data submission to the lead partner at the end of March 2025. She indicated that a meeting has been held to address challenges faced by teams in completing this task. In the same vein, Tuuli Lähdesmäki (JYU) invited all WP5 participating teams to write brief descriptions of the data collection process by every team; this would ensure a uniform data collection description in the final reports. Regarding task 5.5, the data is expected to be received by the end of February, and all data collected in local languages shall be translated into English for analysis.

At this point, Katharine Sarikakis emphasised the fact that producing data entails considerable work, as implications are not just organizational or academic but equally entail political dimensions. A specific challenge was raised in the case of Ruken Erdede (KHAS) where the team highlighted challenges in obtaining approval from the Ministry of Education, raising concerns regarding the study's nature of inquiring industry-level questions from students-minors.

Regarding WP5 Jean-François Trubert (UCA) proposed the opportunity of a potential participation of the REBOOT team to present its findings at the upcoming Innovation Forum by EIT Culture & creativity from 22-23 April 2025, in Nice, France. A subsequent meeting has been convened to this effect.

The meeting proceeded with the presentation of WP6 introduced by Caterina Sganga, indicating the progress made as well as upcoming tasks. Specifically, Arianna Martinelli, in her presentation, pointed to the advances made in subtask 6.1.1 - Quantitative mapping of the movie industry in the EU economy. She announced the publication of a blog post titled "*What is the economic impact of the European Film Industry (EFI) at local level?*".

After a summary of WP7 related to dissemination and progress on work update, Gentiana Ramadani presented the advances made on the Social media planning for an integrated communication and briefly introduced two new dissemination (Podcast and Academic Talks) proposals, which were to be elaborated on at the consortium meeting as they required contributions from all participating partners.

WP1 – Work Package 1 (WP1) Project Coordination and Management (UNIVIE)

The coordination of WP1 has been a continuous and structured effort, ensuring that all consortium partners remain aligned with the project's objectives, deliverables, and milestones. Throughout 2024, the project management team has facilitated **quarterly Project Coordination Committee Meetings (PCC)** to oversee progress, address emerging challenges, and refine strategic directions.

A total of four coordination meetings have been scheduled for the year, balancing both online and in-person interactions to maintain flexibility while fostering deeper collaboration. Two online meetings took place in February 2024 and December 2024, providing regular touchpoints for discussion and engagement. Additionally, two in-person meetings were strategically organised: one in May 2024 at the Cannes Film Festival, leveraging the event's industry presence to enhance

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visibility and outreach, and another in July 2024 as part of the EC Review Process, ensuring compliance with reporting and evaluation requirements.

Consortium meetings with advisory board engagement and strategic input

Beyond the PCC coordination meetings, the consortium has gathered at key moments to reinforce collaboration and align efforts across the project. Since the project's inception, two significant consortium meetings have been held:

The Kick-off Meeting in March 2023, setting the groundwork for shared goals and methodologies and a dedicated film festival event at Cannes in May 2024, which provided an opportunity to engage with industry stakeholders and present interim findings.

The first comprehensive Advisory Board report has been finalised as a deliverable, with annual reports and recommendations ensuring continuous refinement of the project's approach. Looking ahead, one major consortium-wide meeting remains: the final meeting in January 2026, anticipated to take the form of a conference or press event, where key project results will be disseminated to both academic and industry audiences.

Project Deliverables and Progress Tracking

Of the total 55 deliverables, significant progress has been made, with 29 already completed as of January 31, 2025, while the remaining 26 deliverables are scheduled for submission until January 31, 2026. The coordination team continues to oversee the workflow to ensure that all outputs align with project milestones and funding requirements.

WP2 Diachronic understandings of the 'competitiveness' and of the 'European' in EFI (UCM)

In this second wave of deliverables, WP2 completed three reports that were included in the tasks 2.2 that explores the specific implementation of EU film policies, their impact and adaptation to the national contexts and how these relate to the concepts of European and competitiveness in the last 25 years and T2.3 that deal with the key film industry stakeholders' experiences of recent technological, policy, and cultural changes. The first task was lead by the team at UCM, the second by the team at UGENT. The three reports are "Cross-national report on European VOD platforms" (D2.2, part of T2.2) prepared by the UCM and UW; "Comparative analysis report on national film agencies", prepared by the UCM, UW and JYU (D2.3, part of T2.2) and "Lessons from the past.

European film industry looks back at thirty years of changes, challenges, and paradoxes”, prepared by UGENT and UCM (D2.4, part of T2.4)

Key findings:

D2.2 Report Cross-national report on European VOD platform

The results of the D2.2 report derived from a qualitative approach study that traced the historical transformation of the streaming market, and analysed the evolution of the EU legislative dispositions for audiovisual content and its impact on the Polish and Spanish legal frameworks. The report provided a content assessment of the catalogue of three selected platforms in each country, especially regarding the presence of European audiovisual works following the implementation of EU policies.

As a conclusion, although it is still early to evaluate its long-term effects, the late transposition of the AVMSD in Poland and Spain can be seen as generally positive on the European works quota. Financing obligations should also help foster the competitiveness of the film industry in both countries. In this regard, platforms must continue to promote European content, not only to comply with the Directive, but also to compete effectively in Europe.

On the other hand, and beyond their immediate impact on funding, the report believes that the forms of legal and fiscal intervention reported in the national markets (Spain and Poland) have a significant positive effect on the competitiveness of the national and European film industries and recommend continued support for such measures.

Nonetheless, the general observation is also that collaboration with VOD providers has turned into a strategic component for national production companies in Poland and especially Spain.

Finally, the authors recommend that the next Directive be more specific regarding compliance and transparency. This should require VOD platforms to provide detailed, easily and publicly accessible data on their content offerings, especially European and non-national productions.

D2.3 Report: Comparative analysis report on national film agencies

The report explored the transformation of the national film agencies in Spain, Poland and Finland with special regard to the implementation of national and EU film policies, their impact and adaptation to the national contexts and how these relate to the concepts of “European” and “competitiveness” over the last 25 years.

The analysis of the three case studies was completed through a mix of desk-based research of policy documents and official data, secondary sources and empirical qualitative research based on

semi-structured interviews (on-site and online) with staff members of the institutions and other stakeholders of the national film industry who shared their views on the agencies, with coding frames and data analysis. Secondary sources consulted were mainly reports, texts and articles published by scholars working in this field.

Despite their differences, all three agencies work on a mixed model, paradoxically European, of competitiveness. This model is essentially based on finding the right balance between the promotion of cultural diversity and industrial growth. At the same time, the policies could be also seen as a reaction to a legal European framework gradually interested in promoting audiovisual industries in ways that felt menacing for smaller productions or contexts that still see in Europe a market considered hard to conquer.

The report presents the following recommendations:

- To explore other forms of administrative independence that keeps a distance between politics and decisions on support of cinema and help secure the long-term viability and effectiveness of the institutions' work.
- To take the diversity of contemporary audiovisual culture more strongly into consideration in their funding and support systems, adapting thus to different forms of distribution, exhibition, and consumption, to the diversity of productions and audiences without forgetting their primarily cultural commitment.
- To focus some of their resources, beyond their central function in the support of culturally valuable productions, on the promotion of international agreements that enhance the accessibility to and distribution of European films in international markets.

D2.4 Report – Lessons from the past. European film industry looks back at thirty years of changes, challenges, and paradoxes

The report analyses how senior representatives from different sub-sectors of the European film industry (production, distribution, exhibition, policies) perceive, have experienced, and reflect on key changes of the film industry over the past three decades. These changes include digitisation and related technological transformations, shifts in film, audiovisual, and cultural policies, and alterations in the strategies and practices of creating, producing, distributing, exhibiting, and consuming (European) films.

Two teams in Belgium (Ghent University, CIMS) and Spain (Complutense University of Madrid, UCM) conducted semi-structured interviews with 68 professionals from the film production,

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distribution, and exhibition sectors, as well as stakeholders from national and pan-European trade associations, interest groups, and policy institutions. Other participants included representatives from film-related organisations such as film offices, festivals, broadcasters, as well as critics, independent researchers, and academic researchers.

The conclusions of the report focused first on the relevance that film-cultural initiatives hold to ensure the present and future of the EFI. Stakeholders acknowledged the vital role played by institutions such as festivals, (film) schools, museums, archives, and public broadcasters in sustaining film culture.

The report also highlights the necessity of recognising that many of the EU paradoxes may also represent the essence of European cinema. Take, for instance, the much-debated issue of overproduction, usually framed as a problem, while it could be also understood as the natural outcome of a Europe of nations and regions interested in promoting its rich cultural and linguistic diversity.

Concerning policy recommendations, many emphasised the need to move beyond supporting film production and to focus on strengthening initiatives related to exhibition, distribution, and promotion of European films. Another key issue was related to the perceived lack of data and knowledge about audiences. There is a call for a more fine-grained understanding of audience behaviours and preferences, especially in comparison to better-equipped players such as US streamers.

Further policy recommendations included combating piracy, strengthening existing content quotas for European works on streaming platforms, strengthening co-production micro-treaties, investing more in cinema exhibition in markets with underserved or underdeveloped cinema infrastructures, addressing national policy measures regarding tax shelters and other financial support mechanisms that create intra-European competition, investing more in audience engagement in film exhibition, supporting the industry to focus more on underrepresented groups like youth, women, the elderly, and people with diasporic backgrounds.

However, perhaps the most fundamental call from the interviewees was to abandon top-down policies that could harm the EFI's interests and to engage in a dialogue that fully considers the professionals' expertise and experiences as well as the diversity of the industry when developing policies.

UGENT and UCM also worked together on the preparation of a policy brief based on the results of D2.4: Lessons from the past. European film industry looks back at thirty years of changes, challenges, and paradoxes. This was also delivered in January 2025.

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WP3 The institutional context of the EU film industry- ELIAMEP presentation

Most of the deliverables related to WP3 are in progress and will be finalised during this third year of the project. In that relation, all the tasks are progressing in a timely manner and the preliminary results indicate that each task is in good track to achieve the research objectives detailed in the grant agreement. Specifically, only one of the tasks (T3.6) has so far been completed already since month 12, but since it is part of a joint deliverable with T3.2 - the 'Report on the Lux Audience Award & European film Festivals' (D3.1), which is due in month 32 - the findings of both tasks will be uploaded jointly in due course. The only deliverable that has been finalised up until now is the 'Governance and public value report' (D3.2), which together with the 'Recommendations on innovation for European film creators' (D3.4), their progress will be detailed subsequently under T3.3, as it is this task that will result in both the above-mentioned deliverables. The ongoing deliverable related to T3.3 will be due in month 27 of the project (May 2025). Next, the 'Final report on the mapping and EU law of institutional models for the promotion of EFI' (D3.5) will be submitted the following month, in month 28 of the project (June 2025). This deliverable will incorporate the findings of both T3.4 and T3.5, as the former looks at the institutional and policy models across the Member States of the European Union while the latter stays at the EU level of analysis and looks at the EU's regulatory and governance regime to promote its film industry internationally. Finally, in month 30 (August 2025), the last two deliverables of the working group will be due: the 'Policy recommendations' (D3.3), which is related to T3.1, and the 'Public database on EU laws and cross-national frameworks' (D3.6), which will incorporate the data findings from three tasks within the working group: T3.1, T4.2 and D3.6. Each of the subsections below will present in detail the progress within each of the tasks.

T3.1 – EU and Comparative Legal Mapping of the Regulatory Filmmaking Framework (SSSA)

Task 3.1 (T3.1), led by the SSSA research team, is dedicated to the investigation of the international, regional, supranational and national legal frameworks informing and governing the operation of the European Film Industry (EFI). This task aims to provide an insight into the legal norms that regulate the different stages of the film-making lifecycle (i.e. pre-production, production, post-production, including the distribution and exhibition of cinematographic works). To achieve this goal, T3.1 is designed as a comprehensive and cross-national legal mapping exercise identifying, categorising, systematically and thematically listing the legal norms that have a direct impact on the operationalisation of the film-making activities. In this regard, and aligned with the

overarching aims and objectives of the REBOOT project, T3.1 focuses on the rules inherent in copyright law and media/audiovisual law as well as the rules concerning cultural diversity, content moderation and online platform regulation.

In line with its aspirations, T3.1 employs desk-based research to collect data. It adopts a combination of systematic review of the primary sources (i.e. legislation, and case law only where necessary) and the secondary sources (i.e. books and book chapters, journal articles, studies, reports, online sources) of law. The data collected through the systematic review of literature and legal mapping are to be analysed through comparative legal method to assess and showcase the level of harmonisation and/or fragmentation in the legal landscape that govern the EFI. This comparative analysis will lead to a set of policy recommendations addressed to EU and national policy-makers in order to indicate the prevailing legislative gaps that require the EU and national policy-makers and legislators' intervention.

T3.1 began in Month 1 (February 2023), and the final research deliverable is due by M30 (June 2025). The research activities are well in progress. The SSSA research team has completed the international, regional and supranational levels of the legal mapping. The first level, namely the international level, consists of the legal instruments administered by the United Nations and its specialised agencies - specifically the World Intellectual Property Organization (WIPO) and the United Nations Educational, Scientific and Cultural Organization (UNESCO) - as well as the instruments administered by the World Trade Organization (WTO). The second level, namely regional level, consists of the Council of Europe (CoE) instruments; whereas, the third level, or the supranational level, comprise the EU Directives and Regulations related to the activities of the EFI. The instruments and legal norms that have been mapped were consolidated into eight Excel Spreadsheets and have been shared with the REBOOT Consortium through the Consortium's Google Drive repository.

As to the next steps of the research endeavours, the research team will complete the fourth and final level of the legal mapping by identifying the legal norms in the national legal frameworks of the selected EU Member States (i.e. Austria, Belgium, Finland, France, Greece, Italy, the Netherlands, Poland and Spain) which correspond to the norms mapped throughout the first three levels. This last phase of the data collection process and the data analysis process are expected to be finalised by the end of April or mid-June 2025. Subsequent to the completion of these phases, the first full draft of the deliverable will be submitted for internal review. The final version of the report will be submitted to the Sygma portal by the official deadline of the task, hence by the end of June 2025.

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In addition to the ongoing research endeavours in this context, the SSSA research team has performed several public engagement and dissemination activities to share the interim research results of T3.1. Team members, Dr. Pelin Turan and Prof. Caterina Sganga, presented their co-authored paper, entitled *“Common European Data Space for Cultural Heritage: Is the EU Taking the ‘High Road’ from a ‘Single Access Point’ to a ‘Single Market Data’ for Digital Cultural Content?”*, at the renowned EPIP Conference (European Policy for Intellectual Property Conference) in September 2024. The paper was submitted to the JIPITEC in December 2024 and currently under review prior to its publication.

Furthermore, the co-authors contributed to the dissemination activities organised under WP7 by drafting a policy briefing, namely *‘Operationalising the Common European Data Space for Cultural Heritage: The Interplay of Cultural Heritage Law and Digital Cultural Assets’*. This policy briefing, which constituted part of D7.13, was submitted to the Sygma portal in February 2025.

Finally, it is worth noting that the SSSA research team is currently planning the next dissemination activities to promote the research outcomes of T3.1. Dr. Turan and Prof. Sganga will be contributing to the final round of the policy briefings, namely D7.14, by drafting another piece on the Common European Data Space for Cultural Heritage through the perspectives of the EFI and by focusing on the interaction of this data space with the EU data law. Also in this regard, the team is planning another publication to reflect on the accessibility of European cinematographic content by persons with disabilities as well as the efficacy of the EU legal framework to foster and reinforce the enjoyment of cultural content as such by persons with hearing and visual impairments.

T3.2 Analysis of EU initiative promoting the EFI: The case of LUX Audience Award (JYU)

The study on the LUX examined the competitiveness of the initiative on the basis of various economic and non-economic indicators, namely revenues, admissions, countries of release, distribution on VOD platforms, awards, professional criticism, newspaper journalism, and online rating by critics and viewers. The study showed that these indicators are significantly correlated: An increase in one of them is likely to lead to an increase in the others. A comparison of these indicators with the European winners of the much more prestigious film awards, the Palme d'Or and the Oscar for Best Foreign Film, shows that the LUX winners are not very competitive in the global or even European film scene. Some of the films have very low admissions and are not widely distributed or recognised by film critics and newspapers. Our study of LUX award-winning films shows that they tend to be contemporary dramas dealing with serious social and societal issues. We also examined the evolution of the competitiveness of the LUX system by comparing

the winners before and after the system was changed from a prize selected by MEPs to an audience award combining both MEP and audience voting. The results show that the change in the scheme did not have a major impact on its competitiveness indicators, nor on the content or style of the winning films.

Task T3.3: Lived Practices, Principles, Cultural Institutions, and the ‘Fringes’ of Filmmaking and Consumption (UNIVIE) is currently in progress, with one deliverable completed and one ongoing. This task produces two deliverables.

The completed deliverable for this task is D3.2 - Governance and Public Value Report, which has led to the development of a policy brief and a paper presentation at the Zagreb Small Cinemas Conference in November 2024.

The Governance and Public Value Report (D3.2) covered several important insights regarding public support and its effect on the film sector. The research explored the role of public value within the European Film Industry (EFI) across six countries. It highlighted the essential role that public sector support plays in building a dynamic and competitive film industry. Despite the efforts of various stakeholders, government support for public value in the film industry remains fragmented and lacks coordination. This disjointed approach makes it difficult to create a unified strategy that could effectively use public funding to enhance the cultural impact of the film sector and foster a more vibrant film landscape. The report emphasises the need for a more integrated framework to ensure that public resources are used efficiently to strengthen the film industry’s contribution to society.

The findings pointed to five critical areas that are key to the future sustainability and impact of the EFI: competitiveness and distribution, public value and cultural identity, funding and policy frameworks, regional and global perspectives, and future audiences and media consumption.

Deliverable 3.4, Recommendations on Innovation for European Film Creators, which is due for completion by April 2025 is ongoing. D3.4 Work in Progress: The ongoing work for D3.4 -is focused on exploring innovative practices and identifying key opportunities for improving the European film landscape. The research is divided between two partners, with the University of Vienna covering Austria, Greece, and France, and Ghent University (UGent) focusing on Belgium, Spain, and Poland. Key areas of focus include, trends and policies supporting women, youth, and migrants in the film industry.

The current status of the work involves the team conducting desk research, policy analysis, and reviewing the historical pathways in filmmaking. This includes interviews with stakeholders to gain

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a deeper understanding of the present dynamics. The research focuses on institutional policies and internal politics that influence the participation of these groups in the film industry. The report is structured around the role of practice and experience in shaping industry dynamics. It also analyses alternative film festivals in Belgium, Greece, and Austria, exploring their impact on small film industries and how they contribute to the growth of niche, independent filmmaking.

Task 3.4 Promotion of the EFI at the international level: Institutional and policy models across the EU Member States started in month 6 (July 2023) and is led by ULIEGE. It examines a diversified set of national institutional and policy practices for the international promotion of the European film industry in the following EU Member States: France, Spain, Italy, Greece, Poland and the Nordic countries of Finland, Sweden, and Denmark. The research is based on literature review and document analysis, followed by supplementary semi-structured interviews with key informants across public authorities and relevant stakeholders in the selected Member States.

Tasks completed by February 2025: Completion of interviews - 46 semi-structured interviews already conducted in 8 countries; document analysis is completed; first analysis of data has already been completed; collection of market data in 8 EU countries; presentation of preliminary results from the T3.4 at the International Small Cinemas Conference, Zagreb, 5-7 November and at the International Film Festival Rotterdam in February 2025. Tasks in progress: each partner involved in the T3.4 prepared a first draft dealing with its national case under study; submission of the first draft from each partner in mid-February; Goals for the next 6 months: Review of the report from mid-February to mid-April; Aim to make consistent the eight drafts dealing with the 8 EU countries under study; Finalisation of a consolidated draft by end April; Proofreading in early May; Following collaboration with ELIAMEP, submission of the deliverable at the end of May (M28); Preparation of a collective presentation based on T3.4 results at the EUJA25; Preparation of a scientific article at the International Journal of Cultural Policy; Contribution to the public database set up by ELIAMEP.

Key findings (preliminary ones according to semi-structured interviews):

- **National authorities** recognise the importance of EU film cooperation and common arrangements. The principle of complementarity between European and national levels is fundamental. National authorities **should also trust in their own promotional capabilities** because precisely the diversity among different European countries is valued outside Europe.

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- International promotion should mostly remain a national-level responsibility in order to preserve not only the **diversity of European cinema, but also** the prerogatives of Member States
 - **Video On Demand (VOD)** platforms offer significant advantages for promoting internationally national and European film industry. For instance, platforms have revolutionised the economy of heritage films. However, streamers, despite bringing new possibilities for production and for dissemination, could damage the ecology of the national film industry, and so for them, the key issue is the **sustainability of this business model** which also has a clear effect on strategies about the international promotion of the national film industry.

According to Danish and Swedish film professionals:

- **Co-productions have multiple forms of value**, namely: financial, risk management, artistic, audience development, skills development.
- Regarding the **broader industrial environment that contributes to competitive co-productions** stakeholders highlighted, namely: stable framework, diverse cultural workers/talent, openness to collaboration.
- Regarding the **broader policy environment that contributes to competitive co-productions**, stakeholders highlighted, namely: EU co-production arrangements, EU and other treaties and conventions (Council of Europe), strong copyright regulations, fair remuneration regulations. At the national level: social dialogue processes leading to concerted industrial action (namely, streaming levy in Denmark).
- More **EU concerted action is needed to avoid a race to the bottom**.

Task T3.5 – EU law and governance and the promotion of the EFI on the international scene

During the conference, the ELIAMEP team presented key preliminary findings and progress of T3.5. ELIAMEP's team has finalised the review of the relevant literature and the mapping of the relevant EU instruments in place, focusing on economic and other agreements concluded by the EU with third countries and on EU funding instruments. Based on this mapping, it has identified the main dimensions around which the provisions related to European audiovisual works and film in third countries are structured (such as mobility schemes for EU professionals, co-productions, EU-third country audiovisual cooperation in international fora). The information on the mapped EU instruments has also been listed in a database which is part of deliverable D3.6 (Public Database

on EU laws and cross-national frameworks). At the moment, ELIAMEP's team is in the process of conducting interviews with officials from relevant Commission DG's (such as DG Trade, DG Communications Networks, Content and Technology) as well as with representatives of umbrella organisations of audiovisual stakeholders at the EU level. Input from interviews will feed into the analytical part of the research. The other teams participating in this task are also working towards the finalisation of their research: the SSSA team has produced a first draft analysing patterns of cultural cooperation between the EU and the Council of Europe as well as between the EU and the United Nations, while UNIVIE is analysing the gender dimension in EU development cooperation funding for the film industry.

T3.6 Analysis of EU delegations' role in promoting the EFI: The case of the EU Film Festivals (JYU)

Our study of the EUFF showed that the initiative is characterised by a complex organisational structure involving both high-level official actors and local film festival organisations and associations, which usually take on the practical organisational responsibilities and compensate for the lack of film expertise in the EU delegation and the embassies and other representations of the EU Member States. This organisational structure is also reflected in the curatorial challenges of the festival. In line with the objectives of the EU, the discourses of the festival programmes typically emphasise European values such as democracy, freedom, equality, human rights and diversity. Alongside the films and the festival discourses, the side events support such an agenda. However, side events are typically based on one-way exchanges.

The organisation of EUFFs is a balancing act between different objectives. This balancing act seeks to combine the rationales of supporting the film industry and using film for various social and societal activities, such as strengthening intercultural dialogue and international cultural relations. Our analysis revealed the ambiguity of the diplomatic discourses and practices involved in the EUFF, ranging from the top-down approach typical of traditional cultural diplomacy to a strong people-to-people approach.

The analysis of the seven films that either had the most screenings at the case EUFFs or were among the most requested films from the film repository showed that EUFF films are audience-friendly dramas or drama-comedies that deal with even serious issues in an uplifting and hopeful manner. The films do not contain disturbing content such as explicit violence or sex.

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WP4 – The framings and strategies of cinema professionals (ULIEGE)

The overall objective of the WP4 is to define and evidence layers of “international market” and “European Film Industry-EFI” alongside key challenges for promoting film competitiveness to move forward. Through mapping consensual and conflicting views on ‘European, vs. international’, ‘European vs. national’, ‘European vs. transnational’, the WP4 deals with key objectives: provide an operational cross-national definition of “international market” and “EFI” from the perspective of film professionals; develop codes of best practices and other tools to assist non-mainstream film creators dealing with legal constraints and opportunities in their creative efforts; provide a comparative analysis towards the main needs of the EFI across the supply chain and its strengths and weaknesses vis-à-vis its main competitors. WP4 is divided into three tasks:

T4.1 identifies the conflictual and consensual views, priorities and strategies that European film professionals hold towards the “international market”. T4.1 is dedicated to unravelling the diverse perspectives, priorities, and strategies embraced by European cinema professionals in their approach to the international market. T4.1 analyses these topics at the European and national levels.

T4.1 – EFI at the international market: exploring the industrial and professionals’ understandings

Key findings from semi-structured interviews:

The international market is mainly understood as outside the country of origin, with a strong focus on the EU internal market. **EU-based film professionals don't have common strategies for promoting the EFI in the international market.** Many share the perception that “each film is a pilot,” which makes it difficult to establish a unified strategy for the industry. As a result, international promotion is developed on an individual basis, mostly targeting national and European markets. Additionally, marketing and promotional strategies are often not planned early in a film’s development, which affects its ability to reach audiences beyond Europe.

Film professionals argue that since European cinema is marked by diversity and fragmentation, **the audience can not relate to a common and shared image of European cinema, which is confronted by 4.3 findings.** They also resist the idea of targeting specific geographical areas with common strategies, emphasising the difficulty of defining a unified European identity in film.

The role of **co-production is perceived both as an industrial need** for the European film sector, **and as a driver for common learning and professional exchanges**. While they are not seen as primary tools for international promotion, such as film festivals, they serve as a key mechanism for industry growth and cross-border cooperation.

Key findings from survey:

The survey is still active. The results are not final, but we can point out some key trends. About the sample, we have received 348 respondents so far. The survey is representative in terms of gender, age and nationalities.

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What should be the EU's priorities in promoting the EFI in the international market?

To what extent do you assess the strategies of transnational US-based VOD platforms (such as Netflix, Prime, Disney+, etc.) ...

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The research team asked professionals from a list of features, to rate each feature about its importance to the competitiveness in the EFI. On the one hand, more than 75% of respondents perceive that the diverse cultural offer, the governmental financial support and the recognition in festivals are very important features to the competitiveness in the EFI. An important aspect is also the collaboration among national funding schemes and the storytelling (innovative and original). On the other hand, respondents perceive that the high production budgets, the technological advancement and the large film companies are not so important aspects to boost the competitiveness in the EFI. The research team also asked a question about the obstacles which prevent the EFI expanding further on the global film market. The most interesting element here is the aspects which received a low number of responses. More than 50% of respondents perceive that Hollywood dominance, limited distribution strategies or limited marketing strategies are perceived as key obstacles. But respondents do not perceive as obstacles cultural differences or lack of EU-wide media companies.

When the research team asked film professionals about what the EU priorities should be in promoting the EFI in the international market, the priorities which received a low number of responses also were quite interesting. On the one hand, more than 60% of respondents perceived that support for the distribution of films across EU countries and outside the EU, and increased investment in marketing strategies should be key priorities for the EU. More than 60% argued that a key priority should be to impose film investment obligations towards various stakeholders including VOD platforms across all the EU Member States. On the other hand, among the priorities

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which received a low number of responses are the following: develop a pan-European VOD platform focusing on European content, develop a EU film brand-label, increase co-productions with transnational US-based VOD services. In addition, respondents seem to be quite reluctant about establishing a European Film Center - similar to the Centre national du cinema in France and expanding the international network of Europa Cinemas.

The research team asked a question about assessing the strategies of transnational US-based VOD platforms. From a positive viewpoint, more than 55% of respondents perceived that US-based VOD platforms really boost content appealing to young audiences. On the other hand, more than 60% of respondents perceived that US-based VOD platforms do not really boost - not boost at all or slightly boost - international competitiveness of the EFI. In addition, US-based VOD platforms do not have a positive impact on the economic growth of the EFI, it is perceived that they do not boost diversity of content across film markets and more than 75% of respondents perceive that US-based VOD services boost American culture/Americanisation. Finally, about risks/opportunities of Artificial Intelligence systems, the interesting aspect here is that more than 70% of respondents consider that the use of the AI in the EFI should not be avoided, or should be avoided slightly. Around 75% of respondents consider the AI as a slight or big opportunity for the EFI; and more than 70% consider that the AI will be embraced by young filmmakers. But on the other hand, they recognise several risks related to the use of AI. More than 60% of respondents consider AI as a big risk for the fair remuneration of creators. They consider strong risks related to the promotion of more diverse content in VOD online catalogues and more broadly risks to cultural diversity and gender parity. To conclude, respondents recognise the opportunity of the AI in the EFI but they express strong reservations about the current use of the AI.

Task 4.2 Coping strategies of creative non-mainstream filmmakers and codes of best practices (SSSA)

Task 4.2 (T4.2) is pivotal to achieving the overarching aims and objectives of WP4, which is dedicated to investigating the EFI's place in the international audiovisual market. As a complementary to the other tasks organised under WP4, which centralise market perspectives and market-related research, T4.2 focalises the perspectives of cinema professionals who play an active role in the international promotion of European cinematographic content via contributing to the production, distribution and promotion phases of the filmmaking lifecycle.

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In this context, T4.2 aims to understand the challenges imposed by European copyright and media laws upon cinema professionals' creative endeavours. Specifically, T4.2 seeks the reasons that stem from the European legislative framework and complicate, if not hamper, the availability and accessibility of European cinematographic content in the international audiovisual market, in order to co-develop a set of 'best practices' that would guide cinema professionals and help them navigate through these challenges.

T4.2, while addressing the needs and expectations of all cinema professionals, pays special attention to 'non-mainstream' cinema professionals, whose perspectives have not been heard in the scholarship. Without necessarily aiming to articulate an authoritative definition for the concept, T4.2 selects three categories of 'non-mainstream' cinema professionals:

1. Short-movie and documentary producers,
2. Independent or art-movie producers, and
3. Producers belonging to national minorities or produce films in minority languages.

In line with its aims and objectives, T4.2 adopts an eclectic methodology combining a systematic literature review with so-called stakeholder workshops to collect data. Systematic literature review constitutes the preliminary step of the data collection process. In this regard, meticulous research has been performed to identify and review the scholarly literature as well as the studies and reports produced, mainly, by the European Audiovisual Observatory (EAO) to map and enlist the legal hurdles cinema professionals experience to produce, distribute and promote European cinematographic works.

As of January 2025, significant progress has been achieved in the context of T4.2. The systematic review of literature has been completed. This effort also revealed the pervasive knowledge gap in the literature as the vast majority of the sources reviewed have been produced and published by EAO in the first decade of the 2000s, primarily because of the advancement of the audiovisual technologies at the time and the proliferation and widespread use of alternative distribution channels, such as VoD and online streaming platforms in the late 1990s. The outbreak of the global COVID-19 pandemic has brought this topic to the forefront once again, given that the VoD and other online streaming platforms has gained a tremendous popularity and received a great demand as a result of the COVID-19 restrictions and the closure of the cinema theatres. In the post-COVID era, and while the national and European film industries are developing recovery

plans and strategies, the interface of the EFI and international promotion vis-a-vis the EU legal framework is still an actual topic with unresolved problems.

Based on the information extracted from the systematic review of the literature, three major topics have been identified. These topics are as follows:

- *The hardship* in identifying the copyright holders of creative components or cinematographic works for licensing purposes,
- *The legal challenges*, stemming from the territoriality of copyright and licenses, that complicate the promotion of cinematographic works on TV broadcasts, in movie theatres, and on Video-on-Demand (VoD) platforms,
- *The novel challenges* imposed by VoD platforms and their recommender systems upon the visibility and promotion of European cinematographic content.

The above-mentioned topics have been consolidated into an 'Information Sheet', which also provided information on the REBOOT project in general, the aims and objectives as well as the expected outcomes of stakeholder works. The Information Sheet has been circulated to cinema professionals along with the invitation to the stakeholder workshops.

Stakeholder workshops, as the second step of the data collection method, are designed as semi-formal and interactive online meetings to start a conversation between legal scholars and European cinema professionals. These online meetings aspire to create a safe space for cinema professionals to share their perspectives on the place of the EFI in the global audiovisual market, to vocalise the problems they tackle to produce, distribute or promote cinematographic content - while also becoming part of the solution-making process.

Building upon the key findings of the literature review, the first stakeholder workshop was held on January 24, 2025. Given the busy schedules of the cinema professionals who had previously accepted to attend the workshops, the first meeting was held with the participation of five people. The research team is currently on a quest to enhance the number and diversity of the participants. Since December 2024, the research team has reached out to 70 individuals and 72 organisations, and the team is waiting for responses of the potential participants to pursue with the second stakeholder workshop.

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On that note, it shall be crystallised that the first of the series of online meetings helps collect data by triangulating the information extracted from the review of the literature and updating the major legal challenges identified through desk-based research. However, the second and onward online meetings are driven by the goal of including the cinema professionals in the solution-making process by co-developing a 'code of best practices' with them.

The code of best practices, on the one hand, is envisioned to be a document compiling the ways in which cinema professionals have historically tackled the aforementioned legal challenges. On the other hand, the code of best practices is designed to legally scrutinise such coping strategies to produce a set of legally sound guidelines that would enlighten the practices of other cinema professionals experiencing the same legal problems.

T4.2 and its corresponding deliverable, Deliverable 4.2 (D4.2), is due for submission by M34 (October 2025). The research team is planning to finalise the first full draft of D4.2 by M31 (July 2024) and to submit the deliverable to internal quality review/peer review in M31. Subsequent to the feedback to be received from the reviewers, the research is planning to finalise the report by M33 (September 2025) and submit the final version of D4.2 to the European Commission in M34 (October 2025).

The research tasks performed in the context of T4.2 will lead not only to the open access project deliverable, namely D4.2, but also a couple of academic publications. The research team, Pelin Turan and Caterina Sganga, are currently drafting a theoretical chapter, tentatively entitled 'To (Re-)Define Competitiveness of European Cinema: Legal Framework Informing and Governing the Global Distribution of Copyrighted Cinematographic Works', for the book, *Global Film Europe: Rethinking Competitiveness, Identity and Power* (Palgrave). Also for the same book, the team is co-drafting yet another chapter, tentatively entitled 'Screen Quotas vs Automated Recommender Systems: On the Efficacy of EU Policies and Legal Tool for Enhancing the Global Competitiveness of European Cinematographic Content', which investigates the technologies impact on the enhance or prevent the visibility and accessibility of European cinematographic works on VoD platforms.

In addition to these dissemination activities, the research team is planning to attend the 'Over the Bridge' meetings, to be held as part of the Istanbul Film Festival from 15 to 17 April 2025, in order to present the interim results of the research conducted so far.

Task 4.3 International understandings of ‘European’ in the EFI examines the views of international film professionals towards the EFI in six countries: Argentina, Brazil, Mexico (UC3M), South Korea (ULIEGE), Turkey (KHAS), South Africa (EUR).

The data collection is almost concluded. The team finished the literature review, conducted more than 100+ semi-structured expert interviews, and initiated an international survey (ongoing, 315+ respondents so far) with data collection regarding gender, age and professional role. The data analysis will be completed by June 2025. The next steps are writing deliverable D4.4 and submitting it for internal review until April 2025 to allow for the final submission in July 2025.

The key preliminary findings of survey include:

- What options define the EFI? Top results: Art cinema, Cinema d’auteur, International co-productions – followed closely by State support and freedom of expression
- What are the main strengths of the EFI? Top results: Arthouse cinema, International co-productions, Cultural diversity
- What are the top local needs in non-EU markets? Increased funding access: Access to international film circuit: Improved distribution networks.
- What specific areas should the EU prioritise to enhance institutional support of local film industries? Development of co-production initiatives; Tax incentives and subsidies for film production; Access to international markets and distribution channels.

These preliminary findings are also reflected in the interviews (analysis ongoing):

- Key common challenges faced by the six non-EU markets: supporting independent film production, expanding and strengthening distribution channels, expanding audiences

In terms of dissemination, part of the findings were presented at the International Film Festival Rotterdam (February 2025). They will also be presented to the British Film Institute (March 2025) and at the Istanbul Film Festival (April 2025). Finally, several group chapters based on this work are in preparation:

- Mapping the European Film Industry in the Argentinian, Brazilian, Mexican, South African, South Korean and Turkish Markets: Roles, Trends, and Policy Gaps (to be included in REBOOT edited volume The Governance of Competitiveness in the European Film Industry; submitted)

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- A film market-creating policy agenda for the European film industry – building audiences, alliances, and sustainable film industries in Argentina, Brazil, Mexico, South Korea, South Africa, and Turkey (included in proposed REBOOT edited volume The European Union as a global film enabler: Rethinking power, competitiveness and identity)
 - Strengthening the circulation of the European Film Industry – barriers to a competitive theatrical and Video-On-Demand distribution (included in proposed REBOOT edited volume The European Union as a global film enabler: Rethinking power, competitiveness and identity)

WP5 – Building the future competitiveness (UNIVIE)

For the work and research related to tasks and deliverables in WP5, it is noted that Task 5.1 **Analysis of Young People's Film Preferences in Europe: The Case Study of the Young Audience Award (JYU)** has been completed.

Intensive work continues on Task 5.2, **Survey on young people's film preferences in Europe (JYU)** which involves completing questionnaires by all partners involved in this task. As of the progress report presented at this conference in January 2025, the data are as follows:

UNIVIE: 250/250 responses from students (aged 18 to 24) and 245/250 responses from children (aged 12 to 18)

JYU: 338/250 responses from students (aged 18 to 24) and 162/250 responses from children (aged 12 to 18)

UGENT: 236/250 responses from students (aged 18 to 24) and 235/250 responses from children (aged 12 to 18). 56 respondents didn't specify their age (total: 527)

KHAS: 118/250 responses from students (aged 18 to 24) and 13/250 responses from children (aged 12 to 18)

UCA: Secondary schools approvals obtained, in three different establishments; Meetings with secondary school teachers are scheduled for mid-February

UCM: 255/250 responses from students (aged 18 to 24) and 122/250 responses from children (aged 12 to 18)

UW: 229/250 responses from students (aged 18 to 24) and no responses at the moment T5.5 from children (aged 12 to 18)

ELIAMEP: 240/250 responses from students (aged 18 to 24) and 97/250 responses from children (aged 12 to 18)

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SSSA: 150/250 responses from students (aged 18 to 24) and 50/250 responses from children (aged 12 to 18)

The data collection will end in March 2025.

Task 5.3 ‘The Cognitive Skills Developed in the Creation and Reception of Content in Mixed Reality’ is due for completion by April 2025.

Following the remarks of the research officer from October 2024, and as planned in the initial agreement (Proposal template Part B: technical description, p.2), the team must also explain the reasons why researchers are conducting these tests on spatial cognition induced by classic content and XR content.

For this, it still includes a historical and theoretical part on the links between classic cinema and the XR creative technology sphere, which currently lead to a hybridization of two genres and two technological fields. From this perspective, two questions are answered as follows:

What are the conditions and characteristics of the emergence of XR technologies in the current media landscape?

What are the impacts of XR technologies on social cognition, and from this, on the reception of classic and XR video film content by the broad public?

It has to also characterise the risk of an inequality between social cognition induced by XR technologies and the cognitive framework of classic cinema.

Finally, it considers the historical and future hybridization of classic cinema and XR technologies from the perspective of institutional support (quantitative and qualitative) for hybridization - EU and some extra-European models.

On this level, this ongoing work concerns the comparative multi-scale study of European and extra-European state aids in our field.

Task 5.3 has already covered the state policies and funding aids in the audiovisual/film sector in five European states (Belgium, France, Germany, Italy and Luxembourg). A thorough analysis of the direct public funding schemes, fiscal incentives dedicated to AR/VR/XR has been completed. The findings demonstrate that the EU member states are aligned with the EU policies, but their audiovisual/film sectors remain segmented due to inconsistent funding mechanisms, and national rather than international priorities. On an international level, Task 5.3 also concentrates on the policies and funding schemes of Canada and South Korea. This work is under development and will be completed by April 2025.

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The last part of Task 5.3 involves conducting cognitive tests for audiovisual content and spatial orientation by using the appropriate eye-tracking technology. This part aims to complete the previous D5.3.1. and will give answers on whether young creative persons have more advanced cognitive abilities regarding the reception of immersive cinema, compared to non-creative students - consumers of classic cinema culture.

Therefore is proposed the experimental study of social cognition induced by classical cinema and by hybridization, relative to the representation of space and spatial orientation, as an argument in favour of the new policy of extended cinema aid, the coherence and volume of which are, for us, good tools for increasing the attractiveness of European cinema.

Cognitive testing schedule

Dates	Schedules	Places	Publics	Number of people	Manipulations	Technical equipment	Scientific objectives
Friday March 7, 2025	09:00-12:00	MASH South East	M1 Master Media Design and M2 Master ICCD	Approx. 20 people in total	Viewing VR content.	Eye-tracking built into Varjo VR headset.	Obtain "heat maps" of the VR content viewing session, in order to define the management of attentional points (on the "direction of gaze" side and on the "semiotic affordances of the landscape represented by VR" side, which could influence the spatial orientation "induced" by VR, of the subjects.
					Drawing of the topology of the real site represented by the VR content.	Paper and pencil.	Have drawings performed to assess the subjects' "induced" spatial orientation.
Friday March 7, 2025	2:00 p.m. - 5:00 p.m.	La Napoule Castle (Mandeli eu)	M1 Master Media Design and M2 Master ICCD	Approx. 20 people in total	"Task-based" wandering ("find this room", "exit through this exit", etc.) in the real site.	Stopwatch.	Take measurements of task execution time in order to assess the subjects' "induced" spatial orientation.

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						Tobii eye-tracking glasses.	Obtain “heat maps” of the wandering in the real site, in order to define the management of attentional points (on the “direction of gaze” side and on the “semiotic affordances of the real landscape” side, which can influence the spatial orientation “induced” by the VR of the subjects.
Friday March 14, 2025	10:00 a.m. - 1:00 p.m.	La Napoule Castle (Mandeli eu)	M1 Master MHN	Approx. 15 people in total	Viewing “classic video” content.	Projection of classic video on a screen. Tobii eye-tracking glasses.	Obtain “heat maps” of the viewing session of the “classic video” content, in order to define the management of attentional points (on the “direction of gaze” side and on the “semiotic affordances of the landscape represented by the classic video” side, which could influence the spatial orientation “induced” by the classic video, of the subjects.
					“Task-based” wandering (“find this room”, “exit through this exit”, etc.) in the real site.	Tobii eye-tracking glasses.	Obtain “heat maps” of the wandering in the real site, in order to define the management of attentional points (side “direction of gaze” and side “semiotic affordances of the real landscape”, which can influence the spatial orientation “induced” by the classic video, of the subjects.
Friday March 14, 2025	2:00 p.m. - 5:00 p.m.	La Napoule Castle (Mandeli eu)	M2 Master DISTIC	Approx. 15 people in total	Viewing “classic video” content.	Projection of classic video on a screen. Eye-tracking glasses	Obtain “heat maps” of the viewing session of the “classic video” content, in order to define the management of attentional points (on the “direction of gaze” side and on the “semiotic affordances of the landscape represented by the classic video” side, which could influence the spatial orientation “induced”

							by the classic video, of the subjects.
					<p>"Task-based" wandering ("find this room", "exit through this exit", etc.) in the real site.</p>	<p>Tobii eye-tracking glasses.</p>	<p>Obtain "heat maps" of the wandering in the real site, in order to define the management of attentional points (side "direction of gaze" and side "semiotic affordances of the real landscape", which can influence the spatial orientation "induced" by the classic video, of the subjects.</p>

Task 5.4 Comparative Studies on Creative Production Process for Film Music in Europe

There has been an update and translation of the questionnaire for professional composers from the FAMES and ECSA networks is work in progress by Ms. Stefany Rodriguez (Master's in Music). The questionnaire is now ready to be sent to both composer networks, with feedback expected in the spring. Data analysis will be conducted, with results available by August at the latest. The questionnaire has been sent.

T5.5 Teenagers and Youth: Tastes and Interactions Regarding Transnational and European Filmic Content. Ongoing work continues on Task T5.5 conducting focus groups by all partners involved in this task. Here is the current status of the collected data:

UNIVIE: 35/30 responses from students (aged 18 to 24) and 42/30 responses from children (aged 12 to 18)

JYU: 28/30 responses from students (aged 18 to 24) and 37/30 responses from children (aged 12 to 18)

UGENT: 33/30 responses from students (aged 18 to 24) and 27/30 responses from children (aged 12 to 18)

UW: 35/30 responses from students (aged 18 to 24) and 12/30 responses from children (aged 12 to 18)

ELIAMEP: 19/30 responses from students (aged 18 to 24) and 20/30 responses from children (aged 12 to 18)

SSSA: 34/30 responses from students (aged 18 to 24) and 30/30 responses from children (aged 12 to 18)

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UCA: 80/30 responses from students (aged 18 to 24) and 4/30 responses from children (aged 12 to 18)

The process with KHAS and UCM is ongoing; however, specific numbers are not available at this time.

WP6 – Indicators and recommendations SSSA

WP6 concentrates on socio-economic indicators and guidelines associated with EFI. The WP is structured into three tasks to facilitate this objective, coordinated by the SSSA (ECON team). The initial task, T6.1 (M4-M28) - Socio-economic analysis of Europe's movie industry: quantitative assessment and associated indicators (Lead Partner: SSSA; UNIVIE), is further divided into two subtasks:

ST6.1.1 - Quantitative analysis of the movie industry within the EU economy: Findings from this subtask were presented at the first internal REBOOT Conference in Cannes and submitted as Deliverable D6.1 – Indicators Report (M16). These findings were also revisited during the second internal REBOOT Conference (M24). Therefore, the study explores the direct and indirect impact of the European Film Industry at the country and regional level, focusing on its integration into local economies. Key findings are:(i) The degree to which the EFI integrates into local economies varies significantly across Europe. Some countries exhibit strong local linkages, while others rely more on international supply chains.(ii) The EFI shows greater variability in embeddedness compared to the broader Cultural and Creative Industries (CCIs). Certain regions excel in film industry integration despite lower CCI performance.(iii) Strong embeddedness correlates with higher wages and added value per worker, reinforcing its role in economic development. It also supports interconnected sectors like tourism and manufacturing. From a policy perspective, policymakers should encourage partnerships between the film industry and related sectors to maximise local economic benefits. Additionally, greater attention should be given to developing targeted policies that support less integrated regions, reduce disparities, and foster economic resilience. Another key aspect is promoting cross-border cooperation among key industry hubs to enhance competitiveness and uphold shared European values. The study underscores the need for policies that leverage the EFI's economic role while addressing regional disparities to build a more competitive and inclusive film sector.

ST6.1.2 - Aligning EU movie industry content with the Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs): This subtask was showcased as a work-in-progress during the second internal REBOOT

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Conference. The presentation offered a comprehensive overview of the existing research, methodological approaches, and initial results. Final results will subsequently be incorporated into the Competitiveness Dashboard under Task 6.2.

The second task, T6.2 (M28-M34) - Development of a Film Industry Competitiveness Dashboard (Lead Partner: SSSA; UNIVIE, UCM, UGENT, UW, UCA), was referenced during the presentation, noting its scheduled initiation at M28.

The third task, T6.3 (M28-M36) - Comprehensive policy recommendations and formulation of "A Policy Agenda for EUFilm2030" (Lead Partner: SSSA; UNIVIE, EUR, ELIAMEP, ULIEGE, UCA, JYU), was also outlined during the presentation, confirming its start at M28. Furthermore, the intervention provided a clear timeline for each task, offering an overall perspective on current and future initiatives of the SSSA–ECON team to increase visibility and awareness. No further interventions or inquiries followed the presentation.

WP7 – Dissemination

Regarding WP7 Dissemination, starting with the exact deliverables for this work package, four have been completed: *D7.8 Three informative videos and immersive scenaria*, *D7.9 International Workshop on Music for Film and Visual Media*, and *D7.13 Policy briefings deriving from WP2-5 M24*. During the reporting period, (January 2024-January 2025) 17 blog posts were published on the website. The website itself has seen increased traffic, becoming an informative hub for the industry.

Regular maintenance and content updates have resulted in 2,800 active users, accumulating a total of 16,000 views. At the same time, the project's social media presence has been strategically developed and consistently updated following a structured monthly plan. Engagement metrics show a growing audience, on Instagram and on LinkedIn.

Regarding the newsletter, which is published quarterly based on the latest recommendations from reviewers during the review process in January in 2024, the second edition (January 2025) was released, published on the website, and distributed to the consortium's available emails list.

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Visibility and dissemination activities

UCM Team

Publications

- **Frames of Change: Historicizing Recent European Cinema (1990-2025)** (Madrid, May 2025) – Planned publication.

Conferences

- **NECS 2025 Conference** (June 2025) – Panel: Changes and Challenges: Cultural Policies and the European Film Industry (with colleagues from UGENT, ULiege, KHAS).
- **Frames of Change: Historicizing Recent European Cinema (1990-2025)** (Madrid, May 21-22, 2025).
- **NECS 2024 Conference** – “Emergencies” (Izmir, June 27-29, 2024) -Panel: Functional emergencies? Looking back at thirty years of the European Film Industry (1990-2020) (UCM, UGENT, JYU). Chair: Andrea Pócsik.
Engelart Willems (Ghent University): Emergencies and Emergence: The Flemish Film Industry.
Kaisa Hiltunen (University of Jyväskylä): A small nation perspective on the European film industry -the case of Finland.
Fernando Ramos Arenas (Complutense University of Madrid): A certain tendency in European cinema.

Presentations & Talks

- **Master in Audiovisual Heritage** (Complutense University of Madrid - UCM)
The Audiovisual Sector in Transformation: State of the Art and European Legal Framework (October 9, 2024)
Speaker: Loreto Corredoira.
- **Challenges of Digitalization of Audiovisual Works / New Platforms for the Exploitation of Cinema: Conclusions of the REBOOT Project** (November 6, 2024)
Speakers: Loreto Corredoira & Fernando Ramos.
- **Public Talk at CEIP Miguel Blasco Vilatela School** (Madrid, April 2025, planned)
Building the Spectator of the Future.
- **Round Table at Málaga Film Festival** – MAFIZ 2025 (March 18, 2025) -On the Competitiveness of European Cinema in the VOD Sector: The Spanish Case.

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Venue: Thyssen Museum Auditorium.

- **Speakers:** Representatives from Atresplayer, Movistar, and Acontracorriente (participation pending confirmation).

Workshops & Coordination Meetings

- **Knowledge Exchange Workshop** (Warsaw, January 22-24, 2025) -Reinventing Public Service Media for the Age of Platforms: Organisation, Culture, and Independence.
- **International Workshop** on Diversity and Audiovisual Services on Demand (Madrid, October 23, 2024) -Round Table: REBOOT Project: The European Film Industry and the Challenges of VOD. Organised by UC3M Audiovisual Diversity Research Group.
- **Internal Coordinating Workshop** for D2.4 (Madrid, June 2024) – Organised by UCM with UGENT and UW.
- **First Internal REBOOT Conference** (Cannes, 2024) -Presentation of progress on T2.2 and T2.3.
- **Ghent University Workshop** (October 2023) -Coordination of shared tasks between UGENT, UCM, UW, ULIEGE, and JYU, with industry participation.

Film Festival Participation

- **San Sebastián International Film Festival 2023** (SSIFF, 71st Edition) (September 22-30, 2023) -REBOOT's UCM research group attended to analyse industry trends.
- **Málaga Film Festival 2025 (MAFIZ)**- Planned participation as part of WP7.

ELIAMEP Team

Publications (Completed & In Progress)

- **Report:** Competitiveness in European Law by Evangelia Psychogiopoulou, Apostolos Samaras, Laia Comerma, Antonios Vlassis & Dealan Riga.
- **Book Chapter** (Submitted): EU law and the competitiveness of the audiovisual sector and the European film industry: The trajectory of an evolving concept? by Evangelia Psychogiopoulou, Apostolos Samaras, and Laia Comerma.
- **Book Contract** (Routledge, 2025): Governance in the Cultural and Creative Industries: Competitiveness, Diversity and Fairness in the EU by Evangelia Psychogiopoulou, Anna Kandyla, Apostolos Samaras, Laia Comerma, Antonios Vlassis, Dealan Riga.

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- **Special Issue Proposal** (Submitted): Cultural Governance and EU External Policies: The Case of Film -Submitted to the International Journal of Cultural Policy.
Editors: Evangelia Psychogiopoulou (ELIAMEP) & Tuuli Lähdesmäki (JYU).
Builds on contributions from the proposed panel at the EUIA Conference 2025.
 - **Paper** (Under Preparation): To be submitted to a peer-reviewed journal, based on D2.1, by Evangelia Psychogiopoulou, Apostolos Samaras, Laia Comerma.

Conferences & Panels

- **European Union Studies Association** (EUSA) Biennial Conference (Philadelphia, May 8-10, 2025) -accepted paper: Trade, Development, and the Cultural Sector: An Impossible Nexus?
- **The European Union in International Affairs** (EUIA) Conference 2025 (Brussels, May 21-23, 2025)
- **Panel Proposal (Submitted)**: Cultural Governance and EU External Relations: The Case of European Film. Panel connects research from T3.5 with other WP3 tasks.
- **12th Biennial Conference** of the ECPR Standing Group on the European Union (SGEU) Universidade NOVA, Lisbon (June 19-21, 2024)
Presentation: "Trade, Development, and the Cultural Sector: An Impossible Nexus?"
Presenter: Evangelia Psychogiopoulou and Anna Kandyla
Panel: Promoting EU Norms through Trade
Paper: Trade, development, and the cultural sector: An impossible nexus?
Presenter: Evangelia Psychogiopoulou.
- **6th Conference on Cultural and Creative Industries** (Patras, December 6-7, 2024)
Panel: Music and Audiovisual Industries
Presentation: "Competitiveness" and "Cultural Diversity" in EU Policies for the Audiovisual Sector
Presenter: Apostolos Samaras.

Presentations & Lectures

- **Lecture at University of the Peloponnese** (May 30, 2024) -Culture in EU Foreign Trade Policy Guest Speaker: Laia Comerma (ELIAMEP)

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UNIVIE Team

Publications

- **Special Issue Proposal** (Submitted): International Journal of Cultural Policy
Cultural Governance and EU External Policies: The Case of Film.
Paper: Shots and Sequence in the EU's Governance of Gender Equality in the Film Industry in EU Development Cooperation Policy
Authors: Katharine Sarikakis & Gentiana Ramadani.
- **Book Chapter Submitted:** Film, Storytelling, and Social Transformation: Cinematic Justice
Publisher: Amsterdam University Press
Title: Face/Off: Youth as Creators of Cinematic Resistance
Co-authors: Katharine Sarikakis, Angeliki Chatziefrimidou, Gentiana Ramadani, Simon Haslauer, Maria Yeroshkina
- **Report:** Governance of Public Value
Katharine Sarikakis, Gentiana Ramadani, Angeliki Chatziefrimidou and Janina Juengst

Conference Presentations (Accepted)

- **CEDIA conference:** Inequalities and Diversity in the Arts and Creative Industries. Behind the Screen: Gender Inequalities in Video Gaming and Film Industries (Birmingham City University, UK -January 2025)
Authors: Katharine Sarikakis, Oleksandra Gudkova & Angeliki Chatziefrimidou
Presenter: Oleksandra Gudkova & Angeliki Chatziefrimidou
- **10th European Communication Conference** (ECREA 2024): Communication & Social (Dis)Order (September 2024)
Paper: "Young People and the European Film Industry: The Governance of 'Near Misses'" (Forthcoming, Palgrave)
Authors: Katharine Sarikakis, Gentiana Ramadani & Janina Jüngst
Presenter: Gentiana Ramadani
- **15th Annual International Small Cinemas** Conference (November 2024)
Paper: Small but Mighty: Fringes Empowering European Filmmaking in Small Markets
Authors: Katharine Sarikakis & Angeliki Chatziefrimidou
Presenter: Angeliki Chatziefrimidou
- **15th Annual International Small Cinemas** Conference (November 2024)
Paper: The Role of Public Service Media in Promoting Public Value through Film Support

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Authors: Gentiana Ramadani & Katharine Sarikakis

Presenter: Gentiana Ramadani

Conference Submissions

- **Association for Cultural Economics International (ACEI2025)**

Paper: Public Value and Economic Impact in the European Film Industry: A Case Study of Austria and Greece

Authors: Gentiana Ramadani & Katharine Sarikakis.

Connects research from T3.3

Knowledge Exchange Workshops & Panels

- **Knowledge Exchange Workshop** (Warsaw, January 22.24, 2025) Reinventing Public Service Media for the Age of Platforms: Organisation, Culture, and Independence.

Panel: Reboot Debate: Cultural Audiovisual Heritage for the Public Good and European Competitiveness

Chair: Michał Głowacki (University of Warsaw).

Panelists: Jacek Mikucki (University of Warsaw), Tadeusz Kowalski (The National Broadcasting Council), Gentiana Ramadani (University of Vienna), Fernando Ramos Arenas (Complutense University of Madrid), Elżbieta Wysocka-Koerber (The National Film Archive Audiovisual Institute), Anita Zawisza (University of Warsaw)

ULIEGE

- **April 2024** – Media Industries 2024, King’s College London

Presentation: “Towards a European Model of International Film Competitiveness: Comparing Existing Indicators with the Views of European Professionals”

Panel: I8 -Assessing Competitiveness in European Film Industries

Authors: Mafalda Dâmaso, Antonios Vlassis, Katharine Sarikakis, and Marina Rossato Fernandes

Presenter: Mafalda Dâmaso

- Cannes Film Festival, Cannes Market, **May 2024** -Presentation of WP4 results.

- **International Workshop** on Diversity and Audiovisual Services on Demand (Madrid, **October 23, 2024**) -Round Table: REBOOT Project: The European Film Industry and the Challenges of VOD. Organised by UC3M Audiovisual Diversity Research Group.

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- **15th Annual International Small Cinemas** Conference (November 2024), paper related to T3.4
 - **February 2025** - International Film Festival Rotterdam (Rotterdam, February 3, 2025)
Panel: Global Film Europe – Rethinking Competitiveness, Identity and Power
Presenters: Mafalda Dâmaso (EUR), Antonios Vlassis - Marina Rossato Fernandes (ULIEGE), & Isabela Vargas Miranda (UC3M). Moderated by Pedro Tinen.
 - **February 2025** - International Film Festival Rotterdam (Rotterdam, February 3, 2025)
Panel: Global Film Europe – Rethinking Competitiveness, Identity and Power
Presenters: Mafalda Dâmaso (EUR), Antonios Vlassis - Marina Rossato Fernandes (ULIEGE), & Isabela Vargas Miranda (UC3M). Moderated by Pedro Tinen.
 - **The European Union in International Affairs** (EUIA) Conference 2025 (Brussels, May 21-23, 2025)
 - **2 co-edited books, 3 chapters and 3 articles related to the results from T2.1, T3.4 and WP4** under preparation. Expected publications from May June 2025 to February 2026.

UC3M Team **Event**

- **International Workshop** on Diversity and Audiovisual Services on Demand (Madrid, October 23, 2024). Organised by UC3M Audiovisual Diversity Research Group.
Round Table: REBOOT Project: The European Film Industry and the Challenges of VOD.
Presenters: Fernando Romas (UCM), Antonios Vlassis (ULIEGE) & Isabela Vargas Miranda (UC3M).

Conference

- **February 2025** – 8th Congreso Nacional ULEPICC-España (Santiago de Compostela, February 6-7, 2025)
Presentation: “La circulación de películas europeas en América Latina: situación actual en los principales mercados”
Presenters: Isabela Vargas Miranda & M. Trinidad García Leiva (UC3M)

Presentation

- **February 2025** - International Film Festival Rotterdam (Rotterdam, February 3, 2025)
Panel: Global Film Europe – Rethinking Competitiveness, Identity and Power

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Presenters: Mafalda Dâmaso (EUR), Antonios Vlassis - Marina Rossato Fernandes (ULIEGE), & Isabela Vargas Miranda (UC3M). Moderated by Pedro Tinen.

Publications (Completed & In Progress)

- **Book Chapter** (Submitted): Mapping the European Film Industry in the Argentinian, Brazilian, Mexican, South African, South Korean and Turkish Markets: Roles, Trends, and Gaps (to be included in REBOOT edited volume The Governance of Competitiveness in the European Film Industry; submitted)

Authors: Mafalda Dâmaso, Luis Albornoz, M^a Trinidad García Leiva, Isabela Vargas Miranda, Antonios Vlassis, Marina Rossato Fernandes, Lucile Coenen, Elif Akcali, Melis Behlil, Ruken Doğu Erdede.

- **Article for Special Issue** (Under Preparation): International Journal of Cultural Policy Cultural Governance and EU External Policies: The Case of Film.

Article: EU Initiatives to Promote Film Circulation in Latin American Markets

Authors: Luis Albornoz, Maria Trinidad Garcia Leiva and Isabela Vargas Miranda.

UCA Team

Conferences

- **International conference Femininities and Music on Screen: Creation, Representations, and Identities** (Tours, November 25–27, 2024).

Presentation: From Experimentation to Song: The Sonic Worlds of Julie Roué”,

Presenter: Julie Mansion-Vaquié “

This presentation explored the creative process of composer Julie Roué, drawing on research from REBOOT’s WP5.5, which examines the various stages of the creative process.

Event

Event Report:

- **La Semaine du Son de l’UNESCO – Nice 2023**

The UNESCO Week of Sound, held in Nice from 20 to 29 January 2023, provided a forum for discussing sound-related creativity, technological advancements, and professional trajectories. The event hosted at the Georges Méliès Campus in Cannes, offered a multidisciplinary programme that combined artistic creation with technical and professional

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perspectives, facilitating a holistic examination of contemporary developments in sound studies. On 27 January, the symposium focused on the symbiotic relationship between sound, digital technologies, and creative methodologies. Franck Dufour introduced the concept of *chansigne*, elucidating the intersemiotic translation mechanisms involved in rendering sign language into musical performance. This aligns with recent research on multimodal communication, which explores how meaning is constructed across different semiotic systems (Kress, 2010). Laurent Koppitz presented the F.A.M.E.S. Project, which engages with novel methodologies in sound production. The day further featured an exposition on the KINO Project by Noah Morris and Lucas Benevaut, followed by an intervention from Julie M. Vaquié and Jean-François Trubert on the Horizon Europe REBOOT Project, which investigates the evolving paradigms of film music composition in the digital era. This discourse resonates with current scholarly inquiry into digital creativity and the reconfiguration of compositional practices through emergent technologies (Born & Devine, 2015).

- **SAWA Convention 2024 – Nice**

The SAWA (Screen Advertising World Association) Convention 2024, held from 11 to 14 February at the Hyatt Regency Palais de la Méditerranée in Nice, brought together preeminent industry figures in cinema advertising, marketing, and audience engagement. The convention explored the post-pandemic recovery of the cinema industry, the evolution of advertising methodologies, and the transformative implications of new technologies on audience interaction.

One of the key discussion points revolved around programmatic advertising in cinema, with contributions from Stefan Kuhlow (Weischer.Cinema), Robert Brown (Cineplex Entertainment), and Mike Rosen (NCM). These contributions reflect an overarching shift towards automation and personalisation in advertising methodologies, mirroring broader developments in digital marketing strategies (Lambrecht & Tucker, 2019). The event comprised a session on High Dynamic Range (HDR) projection technologies, delivered by Tom Bert (BARCO) at the Cineum in Cannes, which enumerated technological advancements in cinematic visual standards. A particularly noteworthy session was devoted to academic perspectives on creativity in industry practices, led by Jean-François Trubert and Julie Mansion-Vaquié (Université Côte d'Azur), with particular focus on film music and sound design. Their intervention explored the intersection between artistic research and industry practices, particularly in the realm of film music and sound design.

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This approach is in line with the prevailing academic discourse on creative industries and practice-based research, which advocates for greater synergies between academia and industry (Hearn et al., 2018).

- **International Film Festival of Cannes (May 2024):**

The REBOOT team project has been invited to the MarketPlace of the International Film Festival to give an open presentation of the REBOOT project, accessible to accredited people inside the marketplace. The REBOOT project investigates the dynamics of the European Film Industry (EFI) and its competitiveness within both the European and global markets. Through an extensive qualitative and quantitative research approach, the project aims to identify key trends, structural challenges, and policy implications affecting the sector. This presentation took place at the Palais des Festivals (Cannes) on 15th May 2024.

- **The Innovation Forum**, a two-day event will be held in Nice on April 22–23, 2025, is being organised within the EIT Culture & Creativity. The EIT Culture & Creativity is an EU-funded institute acting as an expert and economic accelerator. Jean-François is a founding member of this institute. It includes the evaluation of projects, their classification according to priority areas, and provides strategic insights (<https://eit-culture-creativity.eu/>).

JYU Team

Conference and Seminar presentations:

- NECS conference, Izmir, Joint panel at NECS 2024 Conference Emergencies (06-27/29-2024, Izmir) Participants: Engelart Willems, Kaisa Hiltunen, Fernando Ramos.
- Kaisa Hiltunen; a presentation in the Seminar of the Finnish Society for Cinema Studies, University of Helsinki, 11 November 2023.
- Tuuli Lähdesmäki's presentation in a Conference "Tangible and Intangible Cultural Heritage: A Dichotomy under Debate", 24-25 October, 2024, Sibiu, Romania.

Forthcoming (submitted/accepted):

- Kaisa Hiltunen & Tuuli Lähdesmäki – The Young Audience Award: Cultivating Future Audiences for European Cinema. In *The Governance of Competitiveness in the European Film Industry*, Katharine Sarikakis, Mafalda Dâmaso, Tuuli Lähdesmäki, Fernando Ramos Arenas, Antonios Vlassis (eds.). Palgrave Macmillian.

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- Tuuli Lähdesmäki & Kaisa Hiltunen – Governing the European Film Industry by Prizes: The European Film Awards and the LUX European Audience Film Award. In *The Governance of Competitiveness in the European Film Industry*, Katharine Sarikakis, Mafalda Dâmaso, Tuuli Lähdesmäki, Fernando Ramos Arenas, Antonios Vlassis (eds.). Palgrave Macmillian.
 - Katharine Sarikakis, Antonios Vlassis & Tuuli Lähdesmäki – Introduction: The Governance of Competitiveness in the European Film Industry. In *The Governance of Competitiveness in the European Film Industry*, Katharine Sarikakis, Mafalda Dâmaso, Tuuli Lähdesmäki, Fernando Ramos Arenas, Antonios Vlassis (eds.). Palgrave Macmillian.
 - Kaisa Hiltunen & Tuuli Lähdesmäki – Young Audience Award ja eurooppalaisen nuorten elokuvan edistäminen [Young Audience Award and Promoting European Youth Film]. Accepted, Kulttuurintutkimus, 2025.
 - Tuuli Lähdesmäki, Mafalda Dâmaso, Kaisa Hiltunen, Ruken Doğu Erdede, Elif Akçalı & Melis Behlil – Developing the EU Film Festival into a two-way event with a clear international cultural relations approach, Policy Brief, January 2025.

SSSA Team

Conference

- **EPIP (European Policy for Intellectual Property) 2024 Conference** (September 2024) - “Is the EU Taking the ‘High Road’ from a ‘Single Access Point’ to a ‘Single Market for Data’ for Digital Cultural Content?” (Presentation of the co-authored paper presented by Pelin Turan & Caterina Sganga).

Journal Article

- Pelin Turan and Caterina Sganga (SSSA), “Is the EU Taking the ‘High Road’ from a ‘Single Access Point’ to a ‘Single Market for Data’ for Digital Cultural Content?” (Submitted to JIPITEC in December 2024, currently under review).

Public engagement events

- **BRIGHT-NIGHT: European Night of Researchers** (September 2024; Pisa, Italy) - Project presentation by Denise Amram, Pelin Turan, Piergiorgio Pilo and Veronica Punzo (SSSA).
- **Internet Festival** (October 2024; Pisa, Italy) - Project presentation through dissemination of information sheets and invitation to take part in the survey conducted in the context of Task 3.5 (SSSA).

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Forthcoming (April 2025 onward)

Book chapters

- Caterina Sganga and Pelin Turan, 'A Panoptic View of the Common European Data Space for Cultural Heritage Through the Lens of the European Film Industry' in Katharine Sarikakis, Mafalda Dámaso, Tuuli Lähdesmäki, Fernando Arenas Ramos and Antonios Vlassis (eds), *Rethinking Competitiveness of the European Film Industry* (Palgrave, Forthcoming 2025)
- Pelin Turan and Caterina Sganga, "To (Re-)Define Competitiveness of European Cinema: Legal Framework Informing and Governing the Global Distribution of Copyrighted Cinematographic Content" in Antonios Vlassis (ed), *Global Film Europe: Rethinking Competitiveness, Identity and Power* (Palgrave, Due April 2025)
- Pelin Turan and Caterina Sganga, "Screen Quotas vs Automated Recommender Systems: On the Efficacy of EU Policies and Legal Tools for Enhancing the Global Competitiveness of European Cinematographic Content" in Antonios Vlassis (ed), *Global Film Europe: Rethinking Competitiveness, Identity and Power* (Palgrave, Due April 2025)

Journal article

- Pelin Turan and Caterina Sganga, "European Union's Cultural Policies at the Intersection of Global Trade Talks and Internal/Single Market" (*International Journal for Cultural Policy*, Due April 2025)

Public engagement events

- **Istanbul Film Festival** (April 2025; Istanbul, Turkey) - Presentation of the research results of Task 4.2 by Pelin Turan (SSSA) at the REBOOT Panel with KHAS and ULIEGE.
- **BRIGHT NIGHT: European Night of Researchers** (September 2025; Pisa, Italy) - Presentation of research results of Task 3.1, Task 4.2, and WP6 by Pelin Turan and Piergiorgio Pilo (SSSA).

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UW Team

Conference

- **Media practices in a digitised world**, Jagiellonian University in Kraków, Poland (October 17-18, 2024), Michał Głowacki, Jacek Mikucki, Alicja Waszkiewicz-Raviv and Anita Zawisza;
- **Central European Congress of Modernization**, Rzeszów, Poland (October 25, 2024), Alicja Waszkiewicz-Raviv;
- **Film Studies and Media Studies in the Horizon of Humanities**, conference, Kamień Śląski, Poland (November 28-30, 2024), Anita Zawisza;

Workshops

- Michał Głowacki, Anita Zawisza, „**Bi Sheng - Gutenberg Workshop. Next Generation**” in **Shanghai & Beijing**, China (November 10-17, 2024), paper delivered: Competitiveness of audiovisual media: the case of Poland”.
- Organisation of the “**Reinventing Public Service Media for the Age of Platforms**” workshop in Warsaw – Reboot in collaboration with Chanse funded project PSM-AP, Warsaw, Poland (January 22–24, 2025);
- **Internal Coordinating Workshop for D2.4** (Madrid, June 2024) – Organised by UCM with UGENT and UW.

Publications (in progress):

- Article submitted: “The Governance of Competitiveness in the European Film Industry”, Palgrave, Alicja Waszkiewicz-Raviv, Anita Zawisza.
- Chapter submitted in monograph “Campaigns, influencers, and likes: Promotion of films and series from a local and global perspective”, Łódź Film School, paper: *The role and function of distributors in film promotion. Based on the activities of Gutek Film and M2 Films*, Anita Zawisza.

Media appearance:

- Interview for AnywhereTV with Anita Zawisza, July 2024, main theme: “Cinema is the cure for all...”. About the Reboot Project in general.

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Screenshots from 2nd wave outcomes interim conference (January, 2025)

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Disclaimer

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Contact

Website: www.thereboot-project.eu

E-Mail: reboot.2023@univie.ac.at

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REBOOT Contributors

universität
wien

ΕΛΙΑΜΕΠ
ELIAMEP

UNIVERSIDAD
COMPLUTENSE
MADRID

KADİR HAS
ÜNİVERSİTESİ

Erasmus
University
Rotterdam

UNIVERSITEIT
GENT

uc3m

Universidad Carlos III de Madrid
Instituto Universitario del Cine Español

Sant'Anna
School of Advanced Studies - Pisa

UNIVERSITÉ
CÔTE D'AZUR

JYVÄSKYLÄN YLIOPISTO
UNIVERSITY OF JYVÄSKYLÄ

UNIVERSITY
OF WARSAW

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